

AFRICA INSTITUTE OF GRADUATE STUDIES

SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES

COLLEGE OF PUBLIC HEALTH NUTRITION

THESIS TITLE: VACCINATIONS AND DEWORMING COVERAGES AMONG UNDER FIVE YEARS

CHILDRENS IN JIGJIGA: PUBLIC HEALTH ASSESMENT, JUNE, 20205,

BY

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Abstract

Vaccination is a simple, safe, and effective way of protecting childrens against harmful diseases, before you come into contact with them. Preventive chemotherapy is an important part of a comprehensive package to eliminate morbidity due to soil-transmitted helminthes in at-risk populations. Vaccines protect against infectious diseases such as measles, polio, tuberculosis, and pneumonia, rota ,dipteria, tetanus. while Deworming programs focus on eliminating GIT parasites that contribute to **malnutrition, anemia, stunted growth, and cognitive impair**.the study assesses the vaccination and deworming coverage among children under five and identify associated factors.the study assesses the vaccination and deworming coverage among children under five and identify associated factors. Community based crosssectional study was conducted among care givers using proportional and spatial random sampling . data were analyzed using descriptive statistics anova, chsquare and logistic regressions via epiinfo. Coverage rates 96.2%, 42.2% and 28% in vaccinations, dewormings and received awreness on vaccinations and dewormings was reached. education and employed (workengagement) are two independent variables significantly associated with full vaccinations and deworming uptake .received awreness/health education increased uptakes .awareness on schedule reduced missed vaccines.indepth interview on policy makers and health workers revelealed critical implementation challenges affecting both interventions (vaccination and dewormings) and programmes in jigjiga . .key issue included in consisitance stock supply, , limited refresher training, , low community awareness and gaps in health education out reaches .healthworkers emphasized the need for improved logistics and better support for defaulters tracking . facility observations indentified stock out of deworming tablet and occational cold chain interruptions , despite genarraly adequate vaccine vaccine storage .policy makers acknowledge the efforts of routine service and campains like BIGcatch and BIRI, but the stressed need for stronger integrations of deworming with immunizations and targeted strategies to reach underserved urban sub kebeles .

1. INTRODUCTION

Vaccination is a simple, safe, and effective way of protecting you against harmful diseases, before you come into contact with them. It uses your body's natural defenses to build resistance to specific infections and makes your immune system stronger. Vaccines train your immune system to create antibodies, just as it does when it's exposed to a disease. However, because vaccines contain only killed or weakened forms of germs like viruses or bacteria, they do not cause the disease or put you at risk of its complications (WHO, 2024). Preventive chemotherapy is an important part of a comprehensive package to eliminate morbidity due to soil-transmitted helminths in at-risk populations (WHO, 2023)

The vaccine is therefore a safe and clever way to produce an immune response in the body, without causing illness. Our immune systems are designed to remember. Once exposed to one or more doses of a vaccine, we typically remain protected against a disease for years, decades or even a lifetime. This is what makes vaccines so effective. Rather than treating a disease after it occurs, vaccines prevent us in the first instance from getting sick (WHO).

Children under the age of five are particularly vulnerable to infectious diseases due to their developing immune systems, limited access to healthcare, and high exposure to pathogens. These children are at risk of preventable diseases that can lead to severe illness, long-term complications, or even death. Vaccination and deworming are two critical public health interventions aimed at reducing child mortality and morbidity, improving overall health outcomes, and contributing to long-term economic development. Vaccines protect against infectious diseases such as measles, polio, tuberculosis, and pneumonia, while deworming programs focus on eliminating intestinal parasites that contribute to malnutrition, anemia, stunted growth, and cognitive impairment. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), immunization prevents 4-5 million deaths every year, while mass deworming programs have been linked to improved nutritional status, physical growth, and school performance (WHO, 2020).

Vaccination programs, particularly those targeting diseases like measles, diphtheria, tetanus, and polio, have significantly reduced child mortality rates worldwide. The effectiveness of immunization in preventing outbreaks and reducing child deaths has been well documented, contributing to the global decline in vaccine-preventable diseases (VPDs). For example, the introduction of the measles vaccine in the 1960s has led to a reduction in global measles deaths by 73% between 2000 and 2018 (WHO, 2020). Furthermore, deworming, which is often administered through mass drug administration (MDA) campaigns, helps eliminate soil-transmitted helminths (STH), a common cause of malnutrition and anemia, particularly in tropical regions. The World Bank has reported that deworming has resulted in improved academic performance, growth, and overall productivity in affected populations (Jukes et al., 2008).

In Ethiopia, vaccination and deworming programs have made considerable strides, particularly in urban areas. The Ethiopian government has made a significant commitment to childhood

immunization, with a national immunization coverage rate of around 75% for routine vaccines (EPI, 2020). However, challenges remain in achieving universal coverage, especially in rural and underserved regions. In the Somali region, where Jigjiga is located, access to healthcare services is hindered by multiple factors, including nomadic lifestyles, insecurity, and limited infrastructure. These challenges, coupled with socio-cultural barriers and misconceptions about vaccination, contribute to disparities in immunization and deworming coverage. Recent reports indicate that some districts in the Somali region have significantly lower vaccine coverage rates compared to national averages, with measles vaccination rates as low as 50% (UNICEF, 2021).

The role of deworming programs is also critical in the Somali region, where the prevalence of soil-transmitted helminths remains high. According to a study conducted in the region, nearly 40% of children under five years of age were found to be infected with intestinal worms, leading to complications such as stunted growth and reduced school performance (Tadesse et al., 2021). Although deworming campaigns have been implemented in the country, their coverage is often incomplete, and the sustainability of such efforts remains a concern. The lack of awareness about the benefits of deworming and the challenges related to delivering mass treatments to remote and hard-to-reach areas further complicate the effectiveness of these programs.

Ensuring comprehensive vaccination and deworming coverage is critical for achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3, which seeks to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages. Immunization and deworming interventions directly contribute to the reduction of preventable child deaths, enhanced educational outcomes, and improved economic productivity. However, significant barriers persist in fully realizing these goals, particularly in low-resource settings like Ethiopia. Factors such as inadequate healthcare infrastructure, vaccine hesitancy, limited access to clean water and sanitation, and logistical challenges in reaching remote populations continue to impede progress. These barriers highlight the need for tailored interventions and policies that address the unique challenges faced by communities in different regions.

In response to these challenges, a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing vaccination and deworming uptake is essential. This includes assessing parental knowledge and attitudes towards vaccines and deworming, examining healthcare delivery systems, and understanding the **local socio-cultural** dynamics that may influence health-seeking behaviors. Furthermore, evaluating the effectiveness of current interventions, identifying gaps in coverage, and exploring strategies for improving service delivery are critical steps in achieving universal coverage for immunization and deworming programs. Research into these areas provides valuable insights for policymakers, health practitioners, and international organizations working to improve child health outcomes in Ethiopia and other similar contexts.

This paper aims to assess the effectiveness of vaccination and deworming programs for children under five in Jigjiga, Ethiopia. Specifically, the study examines the barriers to program implementation, the factors influencing parental decisions, and the impact of these interventions on child health outcomes. By analyzing epidemiological data, existing policies, and community-level factors, this paper provides evidence-based recommendations for improving immunization and

deworming coverage in the Somali region. The goal is to contribute to the strengthening of public health programs that ensure every child, regardless of geographic location or socio-economic status, receives the necessary protection against infectious diseases and parasitic infections.

Statement of the Problem: Despite global efforts to improve child health, vaccination and deworming coverage in children under five remains suboptimal in many regions. Low coverage rates contribute to preventable illnesses, malnutrition, and mortality. In Ethiopia, national immunization efforts have improved coverages in many regions but disparities persist, particularly in marginalized areas. The Somali regional states consistently report among the lowest vaccinations and deworming coverages in the country, compounded by challenges such as nomadic lifestyle, limited infrastructure, and socio-cultural barriers.

2. Objectives of the Study:

- **General Objective:** the study assesses the vaccination and deworming coverage among children under five and identify associated factors.
- **Specific Objectives:**
 - Determines the coverage rates of vaccination and dewormings among children under five.
 - Identifies demographic, socioeconomic, and health-related factors influencing coverage.
 - Evaluates caregivers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding vaccination and dewormings

3. Research Questions:

- What is the current vaccination and deworming coverage among children under five?
- What factors are associated with the coverage rates?
- How do caregivers' knowledge and practices impact coverage and challenges in health care delivery.

4. Significance of the Study: This study provides valuable insights into the factors affecting vaccination and deworming coverage in children under five. The findings will assist policymakers, healthcare providers, and community organizations in developing targeted interventions to improve child health outcomes and reduce preventable diseases. Additionally, the study contributes to the body of knowledge required for achieving universal health coverage and SDGs.

5. Delimitation of the Study: The study focus on children under five years of age in [specific location or community]. It will examine vaccination and deworming coverage rates and factors affecting them within a defined time frame. The study excludes children over five years or interventions unrelated to vaccinations and dewormings.

6. Operational Definition of Key Terms:

- **Vaccination Coverage:** The proportion of children under five who have received the recommended vaccines for their age.
- **Deworming Coverage:** The percentage of children under five who have received deworming treatment according to national guidelines.
- **Under-Five Children:** Children aged between 0 to 59 months.
- **Caregivers' Practices:** Actions taken by parents or guardians to ensure their child's health, including vaccination and deworming.

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Vaccines and immunization: What is vaccination? 23 April 2024 | Questions and answers

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3.Literature Review: Vaccination and Deworming Among Children Under Five

The literature on vaccination and deworming programs for children under five years of age is extensive, with studies highlighting their significant impact on reducing child mortality, improving health outcomes, and contributing to socio-economic development. Both interventions are key components of public health strategies aimed at improving child health in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), including Ethiopia. This literature review aims to explore the body of research concerning the effectiveness, challenges, and strategies related to vaccination and deworming among children under five, with a specific focus on Ethiopia and similar contexts.

A.Vaccination: Global Perspective

Vaccination is one of the most cost-effective and powerful public health interventions, significantly reducing the burden of preventable diseases worldwide. The global expansion of immunization programs over the past few decades has contributed to a dramatic reduction in childhood mortality and morbidity. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), immunization has prevented approximately 2-3 million deaths each year from diseases such as diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis, and measles (WHO, 2019). Immunization programs, through the provision of vaccines for diseases like polio, tuberculosis, and hepatitis, have led to a substantial decline in mortality rates in children under five years.

Africa, significant progress has been achieved. Nevertheless, overall coverage rates remain low compared to the Global Vaccine action plan (GVAP: 2011–2020) targets. In 2018, coverage with DPT-3 and measles vaccine was 76% and 74% respectively. While 76% of the children were vaccinated for Haemophilus influenza-B (Hib) and hepatitis B. Nearly one-third of African countries did not achieve 80% infant PCV3 coverage (Zemenu, et al 2014)

In sub-Saharan Africa, where childhood mortality rates remain high, immunization has been a key factor in reducing preventable deaths. However, vaccination coverage in these regions has been variable like WHO and UNICEF (2020) joint report about vaccinations in sub-Saharan countries including Kenya (DTP 88%, BCG 92%, MCV 90%, polio 90%), Ethiopia (DTP, 75%, BCG 90% MCV85% polio 85%) , Nigeria (56%, 85%,and 75% for DTP, BCG and MCV, 60% polio) respectively A study by Lozano et al. (2012) found that while there was significant progress in vaccine coverage in some African countries, others faced persistent challenges, including logistical barriers, limited healthcare infrastructure, and vaccine hesitancy. Furthermore, the 2019 WHO report revealed that global vaccine coverage had stagnated in recent years, with many countries still

falling short of the recommended 90-95% vaccination coverage necessary to achieve herd immunity (WHO, 2019). These challenges are particularly prominent in rural and remote areas, where access to healthcare facilities is limited, and population mobility further complicates immunization efforts (Gavi, 2020).

B.Vaccination in Ethiopia

EMDHs (ETHIOPIA MINI DEMOGRAPHY HEALTHY SURVEY 2019) report of 44% of children age 12-23 months have received all basic vaccinations at some time, and 40% received these vaccinations by the appropriate age. The percentage of children who received all basic vaccinations has increased by 5 percentage points since 2016 (from 39% to 44%).

the Expanded Programme for Immunisation (EPI) in Ethiopia, launched in 1980, has been one of the core priorities in past Health Sector Development Programmes (HSDPs) and the current Health Sector Transformation Plan (HSTP) (FMOH 2015). The country has mobilised volunteers, health extension workers, and health facilities to deliver immunization services. **Improved district planning and management** were initiated in 2011 with the goal of reaching **every district**. **Static, outreach, and mobile** are the three important service delivery platforms for vaccination services. In addition, several campaigns provide polio, measles, and other antigens to children. **Universal immunisation** of children against the **six** common vaccine-preventable diseases, namely tuberculosis, diphtheria, whooping cough (pertussis), tetanus, polio, and measles, is crucial in reducing infant and child mortality. Other childhood vaccines given in Ethiopia protect against hepatitis B and Haemophilus influenzae type b (Hib) and rota.(2019, EMDHS). According to 2019 EMDHS report on coverage trends. There has been steady progress in EPI coverage over the years. The percentage of children age 12-23 months who received all basic vaccinations increased from 20% in 2005 and 24% in 2011 to 39% in 2016 and 44% in 2019. Also, the proportion of children with no vaccinations decreased from 24% in 2005 to 19% in 2019 EMDHS(2019). At the regional level, coverage of all basic vaccinations is highest in Addis Ababa (83%) and Tigray (73%) and lowest in Somali (19%) but with 59.4% measles vaccination coverages in Somali region accompanied by 0.08% incidence per 100 individuals.

last year (2024), according to WHO and UNICEF estimates of July 2, 2024, Ethiopia vaccination coverage for key vaccines as follows. DPT3 increased from 65% (2022) to 72% (2023) where PCV3 rose from 62% 2002 GC to 69% 2003 GC while MCV1 coverage improved from 65% year in 2002 to 72% year 2003 and at last MCV2 (coverage increased from 48% to in 2022 to 53% in 2023 (cdn.who.int).

[study on](#) status of immunization program and challenges in Ethiopia: A mixed method study (Tariku et al 2024) with result of full immunization in the health facilities in Amhara, Oromia, and Addis Ababa was 56.1%, 70.7%, and 85.6%, respectively. According to this study full immunizations

was 66.4%. the penta1 to penta3 and penta1 to MCV1 dropout rates were 8.6% and 7.4%, respectively. From the total of 16 included studies (Gebeyew biset et al (march 2021) in which 4 studies were conducted in Oromia region, 6 in Amhara region, 5 in South Nation Nationality and People (SNNP) and 1 in Somali region All the studies were cross-sectional in design with the minimum and maximum sample sizes of 173 and 846, respectively. The highest full vaccination coverage was reported in Amhara region (91.7%); whereas the lowest coverage was reported in Oromia region (22.9%).

Ethiopia has made significant strides in improving vaccination coverage over the past few decades. The Ethiopian government has prioritized childhood immunization as part of its national health policy, with a focus on achieving universal health coverage through its expanded immunization program (EPI). As of 2020, Ethiopia's immunization coverage for the pentavalent vaccine (which includes protection against diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis, hepatitis B, and Haemophilus influenza type b) stood at 75%, which is considered a notable achievement in the context of the country's healthcare challenges (EPI, 2020). However, despite these successes, immunization coverage remains uneven across different regions of Ethiopia, particularly in the Somali region. Studies by Tadesse et al. (2019) and UNICEF (2021) have shown that coverage in this region is significantly lower than the national average. reaserch study on Immunization coverage of 12–23 months old children and associated factors in Jigjiga District, Somali National Regional State with The objective to measure the immunization coverage of 12–23 months old children and associated factors in the urban and rural areas of Jigjiga district applied community based cross-sectional survey in two urban and four rural localities concluded 36.6% mohamud abdi ,etal (2014) fully immunized and 74.6% mohamud, etal (2014) were ever vaccinated . mohamud and his coauthors(august,2014) presented immunization coverage rate from card assessment for Bacillus Calmette-Guérin was 41.8%, while for Oral Polio Vaccine Zero, Oral Polio Vaccine One /Pentavalent 1, Oral Polio Vaccine Two /Pentavalent 2, Oral Polio Vaccine Three /Pentavalent 3, and measles were 10.4%, 41.1%, 33.9%, 27.5%, and 24.9% respectively. (June, year 2024 zemenu sheferaw, etal)reported Results Based on maternal recall plus vaccination card 249(41.4%) of children were completed immunization, while vaccination only by card was 87(29.7%). Only 238(39.5%) of participants had good knowledge about vaccination. Not knowing to come back for next visits 197(55.8%) were the major reason for dropout. Residing in urban (AOR = 2.0, 95%CI: 1.0, 3.9), primary educated mothers(AOR = 2.2, 95%CI: 1.0, 5.0), married mothers (AOR = 4.2, 95%CI:1.0, 18), higher average monthly income (AOR = 2.5, 95%CI 1.1, 5.2)and delivered at health facilities (AOR = 3.8, 95%CI 1.9, 7.3)were significantly associated with full-immunization. Factors contributing to these disparities include insecurity, nomadic lifestyles, lack of healthcare infrastructure, and cultural beliefs regarding vaccination. According to a study by Woldemariam and Kidanemariam (2018), vaccine hesitancy and misinformation about vaccine safety are also significant barriers in rural parts of Ethiopia. These challenges highlight the need for more targeted interventions to increase immunization uptake, especially in hard-to-reach areas.

C. Deworming: Global Perspective

The most prevalent nematode parasite worms that affect humans are helminths that are spread

through the soil. The three main species of soil-transmitted helminthes (STHs) are *Ascaris lumbricoides* (*A. lumbricoides*), hookworms (*Necator americanus* and *Ancylostoma duodenale*), and *Trichuris trichiura* (*T. trichiura*) [1]. Due to poor hygiene Soil-transmitted helminthes can be transmitted faeco-orally through the ingestion of infective eggs of the parasites from contaminated food as a result of poor hygiene or direct skin penetration by the L3 larva . Egg deposition begins when the eggs hatch in the colon, mature, and reach adulthood. The vast number of eggs that adult worms lay are discharged through human feces into the environment, where they grow and become infective for humans. Eggs and larvae of STHs can live for several months in the soil (*A. lumbricoides* and *T. trichiura*) and larvae several weeks (*hookworms*) (abdlemenu,etal 2025). 9 million Disability Adjusted Life Years. This report indicates that 260.6 million According to the World health organization 2022 weekly report, STHs are responsible for the loss of 1.Preschool-Age Children,

Deworming is another vital intervention aimed at improving child health. Soil-transmitted helminths (STH) are among the most common parasitic infections in children, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions. These infections can cause a range of health issues, including malnutrition, anemia, impaired cognitive development, and stunted growth (Hotez et al., 2014). Deworming programs, which involve the administration of anthelmintic medications such as albendazole or mebendazole, are widely used to reduce the burden of these parasitic infections.

Global evidence suggests that mass deworming programs are effective in reducing the prevalence of intestinal parasites and improving overall health outcomes. A systematic review by Crompton et al. (2004) found that deworming significantly reduced the prevalence of hookworm and roundworm infections and improved nutritional status in children. Moreover, deworming has been shown to have long-term benefits, such as improved school attendance and academic performance, as children are less likely to suffer from the debilitating effects of parasitic infections (Jukes et al., 2008). The World Bank has highlighted the cost-effectiveness of deworming programs, emphasizing their ability to improve child growth and cognitive development while reducing healthcare costs (World Bank, 2014).

D. Deworming in Ethiopia

In Ethiopia, the prevalence of soil-transmitted helminths remains high, particularly in rural and underdeveloped regions. According to a study by Assefa et al. (2017), more than 30% of children in Ethiopia suffer from soil-transmitted helminth infections. The government has implemented national deworming campaigns as part of its broader child health strategy. These campaigns, often conducted through schools and health posts, aim to provide regular deworming treatments to children in endemic areas. the prevalence of maternal reported deworming supplements among children aged 24-59 months was 15.1%(june, 2021) **Predictive variables significantly associated with deworming** supplementation include maternal media exposure, maternal control of household healthcare decisions, institutional healthcare delivery, and child vitamin-A supplementation

Despite the efforts, coverage of deworming programs in Ethiopia remains suboptimal. A study by Tadesse et al. (2021) in the Somali region found that nearly 40% of children under five were

infected with intestinal worms, highlighting the gap in deworming coverage. This gap can be attributed to several factors, including logistical challenges, inadequate healthcare infrastructure, and low levels of awareness among parents about the importance of deworming. Additionally, deworming programs in Ethiopia are often episodic and lack sustainability, which reduces their long-term impact (Tadesse et al., 2021). The lack of regular follow-up and monitoring also contributes to gaps in coverage, particularly in rural areas where healthcare services are limited. Studies on STHs infections in Ethiopia revealed that infection prevalence varied according to the communities and regions studied. Intestinal parasites, particularly STHs, can thrive in many different locations due to unsafe and inadequate water accessibility, unsanitary living conditions, and improper waste management. In Ethiopia, helminthic infections are a common cause of morbidity [abdlmuner,January,2025) 54.13%(, 1, 2024) of Deworming rate in East Africa reported .

E. Vaccination in the Somali Region

The Somali region of Ethiopia, which includes cities like Jigjiga, has faced unique challenges that hinder the expansion of vaccination coverage. The region's remote location, insecurity, and nomadic lifestyle of its population complicate the delivery of healthcare services, including vaccination. A study by Tadesse et al. (2021) found that only 50% of children in some districts in the Somali region were vaccinated against measles, far below the national target of 90%. Factors such as frequent displacement due to ethnic conflicts, poor road infrastructure, and limited access to healthcare facilities contributed to these low coverage rates.

To address these barriers, the Ethiopian government and international organizations have implemented several vaccination initiatives, such as the use of mobile vaccination units and temporary healthcare posts in pastoralist areas. These efforts, combined with the use of community health workers, have shown positive results in reaching remote populations (Gavi, 2020). However, sustaining these efforts remains a significant challenge due to the high mobility of the population and logistical difficulties in storing and distributing vaccines in the region.

F. Deworming in the Somali Region

In the Somali region, deworming coverage remains particularly low, with many children still suffering from the adverse effects of parasitic infections. A study conducted in Jigjiga and other parts of the Somali region by Tadesse et al. (2021) found that approximately 40% of children under five were infected with soil-transmitted helminths, leading to stunted growth, anemia, and developmental delays. While deworming campaigns have been implemented, coverage rates in the Somali region remain far below national targets.

Cross sectional study (abdlmuner,January 2025) released recently in jigjiga town revealed low prevalancy with r STH rate prevalence of 11.4% overall (95% CI = 9.0, 14.0).

With a prevalent parasite species, *A. lumbricoides* 9.3%, *T. trichiura* 2.8%, and hookworms 0.2%. Of the overall positive cases, 93.1% are due to single parasite infections. 2021 study focused on children aged 2-5 years old in Adadle district of Somali region reported prevalence of 35%

for intestinal parasite infections. This is in the range of the WHO standard of deworming twice a year when prevalence is greater than 20%. *Ascaris* 12.8% of the children. This study identified several factors associated with higher infection rates, including the use of unsafe water sources, shared sanitation facilities, and livestock ownership. National prevalence of schistosomiasis has been reported as high as 73% in northern Ethiopia and 37.9% in the western region.

Several factors contribute to these low coverage rates, including inadequate healthcare infrastructure, limited access to clean water and sanitation, and cultural barriers to accepting deworming treatments. A study by Tadesse et al. (2019) found that many parents in the Somali region were unaware of the benefits of deworming or viewed it as unnecessary. To address these challenges, the government and international organizations have increased efforts to integrate deworming into routine health services and school programs. However, ensuring regular treatment and addressing cultural misconceptions are key to improving coverage rates in the region. Deworming programs have not been held in schools or the community due to a lack of epidemiological studies in the Somali region, particularly in Jijiga town, concerning STH infection (Abdmenur Alawi, Sedo, January, 2025).

G. Challenges and Barriers to Effective Vaccination and Deworming

While vaccination and deworming are highly effective interventions, there are several barriers to their successful implementation in low-income countries. These barriers include logistical challenges, cultural beliefs, misinformation, and limited healthcare infrastructure. In Ethiopia, these challenges are particularly pronounced in rural and remote areas, where healthcare access is limited. Factors such as poor road networks, lack of trained healthcare workers, and inadequate cold chain systems for vaccine storage further complicate the delivery of these services.

In addition, cultural beliefs and misconceptions about vaccines and deworming are common barriers. Studies in Ethiopia have shown that vaccine hesitancy, driven by misinformation about vaccine safety, is a significant challenge in increasing immunization rates (Woldemariam & Kidanemariam, 2018). Similarly, some communities remain unaware of the benefits of deworming, viewing it as unnecessary or irrelevant to their children's health (Tadesse et al., 2021). Addressing these misconceptions through community engagement and education is essential for increasing coverage and improving health outcomes.

H. Strategies for Improving Vaccination and Deworming Coverage

Several strategies can be employed to improve the coverage and effectiveness of vaccination and deworming programs. These include strengthening healthcare infrastructure, improving community engagement, and ensuring the sustainability of interventions. For vaccination, strategies such as the use of mobile vaccination teams, outreach campaigns, and improved vaccine distribution systems have been shown to increase coverage in hard-to-reach areas (Gavi, 2020). For deworming, ensuring regular and sustained treatment cycles, as well as integrating deworming into

routine healthcare services, can **help improve program reach and impact**.

Additionally, addressing vaccine hesitancy and increasing public awareness about the benefits of deworming are critical to improving uptake. Public health campaigns that provide accurate information about vaccine safety and the importance of deworming can help overcome cultural barriers and misconceptions.

Vaccination and deworming are two essential public health interventions that significantly contribute to improving child health, reducing mortality and morbidity, and enhancing socio-economic development. While both interventions have been successful in many regions, challenges related to accessibility, cultural beliefs, and healthcare infrastructure persist, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and rural Ethiopia. To address these challenges, targeted strategies that focus on improving healthcare delivery, increasing community awareness, and ensuring sustainable program implementation are crucial. By addressing these gaps, vaccination and deworming programs can achieve greater coverage and improve child health outcomes in Ethiopia and other low-resource settings.

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4. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY .

A. Study area

The study area is Jigjiga town, the capital and administrative city of the Somali regional State. The town is located in the eastern part of the country, 628 km from Addis Ababa, the capital of Ethiopia. Jigjiga is located at latitude 9.35 °N and longitude 42.8 °E. The mean annual rainfall of 880 mm and the mean annual temperature is 30.4 °C. The average annual humidity is 57.1%. The town has more than 24000 households (HH) and the estimated total population is 257,613. The town has more than 20 kebeles (the smallest administration units). There are seven governmental health institutions (three hospitals and four health centers) that provide services for the town and surrounding population. This study focused on the urban kebeles and excluding rural areas. Jigjiga was chosen due to its diverse population and relatively accessible healthcare infrastructure. The study assess vaccination and deworming coverage for children less than five years of age in the selected urban kebeles, ensuring that the findings reflect the health service dynamics within the city. Major part of the study focused on care givers interview of 213 house holds integrated into both vacine and deworming samples.

The research focused three major health centers in Jigjiga: **Ayardaga, Dudohido, Kordere**, and karama and madina hospital . in addition included private clinic for observations . These facility serve the urban kebeles, which are categorized as follows: Ayardaga (Kebeles 1, 2, 3, 4, 10, 15, 16), kordere (Kebeles 5, 6, 7, 17, 19), and dudohido (Kebeles , 9, 11, 12, 13, 14) . other than mentioned facilities (healthcenters) hospitals like karamarda, madina primary hospital and single privateMCHclinic (dr abdisalan) were reached for interview and observations.The kebeles were selected based on their representation of the urban population (children and their parents) and their proximity to the respective health centers, ensuring the data is reflective of the target group. Mixed methods of quantitatively and qualitative Cross sectional study design was applied to complete.

Sampling done **using proportional sampling and spatial systematic random walk sampling** (every 5th household), starting from central gathering points such as markets or mosques. The estimated number of households per kebele is based on a standard assumption of 0.6 children under five per household (DH), ensuring a sufficient sample size for each kebele. This approach will provide a comprehensive, unbiased assessment of vaccination and deworming coverage in Jigjiga's urban studied populations.

B. Study population

The study population consists of **children under five years of age residing** in the selected urban kebeles of **Jigjiga**, Ethiopia. The target group include both **male and female children** from households within the catchment areas of the health center **an Ayardaga**, three hospitals , **Dudohido**, and **Kordere health centers** . These children are the primary focus of the study as the research aims to assess their vaccination and deworming coverage.

The study included children from households in the following kebeles: Ayardaga (Kebeles 1, 2, 3, 4, 10, 15, 16, 20), kordere (Kebeles 5, 6, 7, 17, 18, 19), and dudohido (Kebeles , 9, 11, 12, 13, 14). Households selected using a **systematic random walk sampling (spatial)** technique, starting from social gathering points like markets and mosques, and continuing with a 5th household interval to ensure an unbiased representation of the population.

The total sample size determined based on the estimated number of households in each localities with an assumption of 0.6 children under five per household. The study aimed to gather a sufficient number of respondents from each kebele to ensure the results are statistically significant and reflective of the urban population's health service coverage.

C. Sample size

Depending on vaccination coverage rate of 19% in Somali region of Ethiopia conducted by Ethiopia mini demography healthy survey year 2019, along 15.1% deworming coverage by getahun (2021) .

integrated sample size of 213 for evaluating vaccine coverage and sample of 164 to evaluate deworming coverage in the study area was reached though reached sample size is below than target

D. SAMPLING METHODS

Sampling techniques are categorized into probability and non-probability methods/techniques of sampling. Different techniques can be applied to survey coverage rate of vaccinations and methods but many challenges arise to apply when sampling is the case. Like using simple random sampling in this case demands list of all households (inaccessible logistically) among all selected kebeles (below) to randomly process in selections. Clustering methods demand large sample more than double accordingly to sample size. Large systematic sampling interval or when applications of systematic random sampling plan is without spatial type, it predicted elongation of sampling period.

Proportional sampling and spatial systematic random walk (5th) interval sampling methods and technique was applied in the field visit to conduct the data based reliability, avoid bias, and at same time representative data collections data, and sampling. Representative kebele/localities (1,2,3,4, 5,6, 7,9,10,11,12,13, 15, 16, 17,18 19 20) was reached after selection to deliver data to analyze based on healthy service catchment areas. Ayardaga catchment (Kebeles 1,2,3,4,10, 15, 16), Kordere catchment (05, 06, 07, 17, 19) AND Dudohidocatchment (09, 20, 11, 12,13, 14). Formula $n/N \times \text{sample size}$ is applied to find sample proportion allocations for each catchments. Spatial systematic randomly walk approach (5th house hold interval) like zigzag movement, selecting market, mosque, social gathering areas to map and do kick start. WHO DHS apply this method to survey urban area. To avoid duplications GBS coordinates was applied in the care givers interview. When one establishment is uncooperative, the event is alternated to next door.

5. DATA COLLECTION AND INSTRUMENT

A. Structured Questionnaire

The structured questionnaire is administered to caregivers of children under five years to assess vaccination and deworming coverage. The questionnaire covered the following key components:

- **Demographic Information:** Age, gender, household size, parental education, and socioeconomic status, work engagement, number under five years /household, family size, kebele/residence.
- **Vaccination Status:** Types of vaccines received, last dates of immunization, missed doses, and reasons for non-compliance, place of immunizations, reason for missing vaccinations, side effect
- **Deworming History:** Frequency and type of deworming drugs administered, Place of deworming, source of deworming stories, reason for missing dewormings,
- **Access to Health Services:** Distance to the nearest health facility, availability of vaccines and deworming drugs, and quality of service provided.

- **Parental Knowledge and Attitudes:** Awareness of the vaccination schedule, knowledge of deworming benefits, and awareness received , other influencing behavior like satisfactions level , suggestions ,

B. Observation Checklist

A checklist used to verify vaccination cards and deworming records, card matches, assess the availability of vaccines and deworming drugs in health facilities and also to asses existance of IEC (informations , communications , and educations . cross-checked the accuracy of caregiver responses.

C. Key Informant Interviews (KII)

In-depth interviews conducted with six policy makers and coordinators, medical directorates or /policymakers, and healthcare providers to understand the challenges and strategies in improving vaccination and deworming coverage.

E. Health Facility Record Review

Immunization and deworming registers was reviewed to cross check of children vaccinated only cause deworming recordings in the area is under developed or cross check and verifications was checked for vaccination only .

6. Data Analysis (EPIinfo7) is applied to run descriptive and statistical analysis.

A. Descriptive Statistics

Basic descriptive statistics calculated to summarize:

- **Demographic Information:** Frequencies and percentages for age, gender, and educational level of caregiver, distance to facility.
- **Vaccination Coverage:** The percentage of children vaccinated against various diseases, such as BCG, DTP, Polio, Measles, etc.
- **Deworming Coverage:** The percentage of children dewormed with medications like Albendazole and mabendazole .

.Statistical Analysis

- **Chi-square Tests:** To compare vaccination and deworming rates across categorical variables such as gender, age group, or caregiver education.
- **T-tests/ANOVA:** To compare means between groups, such as comparing vaccination rates between urban sub kebeles.
- **Logistic Regression:** To identify factors associated with vaccination and deworming uptake, including socioeconomic factors, proximity to health facilities, and caregiver knowledge and educations etc.

References for Data Collection Methods

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 - o Provides an in-depth look at designing and conducting surveys, as well as collecting and analyzing survey data.
3. **Punch, K. F.** (2005). *Introduction to Social Research: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. Sage Publications.
 - o Covers both qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques and their applications in research

7. RESULTS

A. Result introduced Vaccination and deworming coverage of 96.24 % 42.77% respectively.

Individual vaccine coverages.

Bcg 95% opv0 of 93.3% opv 1of 92.27% o pv2of ,87.43% opv3 of 87.43

ipv 1 of 78.83% ipv2 of 70.59% , ipv3 of 84.12%. penta 1 of 89.29% penta2of 87.43%, penta3 of 92.65% , rota 1of 88.14% rota2of 83.64% measles 1 of 78.98%, measles2 of 70.59% , pcv 1of 90.16% pcv 2 of 87.43% pcv 3of 93.20%

B. Socio-demographic characteristics of the study population.

The 213 care giver interviewed were age between 17 -60 years. Six males and 207 females. 136 of them were minimum 1km close health facility were 67 of them were residing below one kilometer away from health facility . 82 of the respondent/care givers were not educated and schooled ever when 69 of them joined primary education , 19 of them secondary school and 40 of them higher educations . 182 of the care givers were jobless when 25 of care givers were involved in job opportunity. 112 household of the respondents /household exposed one child of under five years perhousehold .58House holds exposed 2 childrens of underfive years perfamily .33 of the house holds claimed 3 childrens of underr five age. Only four house holds maintained 4childrens perhouse hold. 85 individuals of the care givers were sourced as daily labour .54 other care givers as bussinees , 49 of them as salarydependents , 10 of the as agricultural dependent .the age of the children ranged between 0month to 59months.

Care givers report 96%ever vaccinated in under five years , 42.77% ever dewormed 68.6% fully vaccinated , 31.4%missed minimum single vaccinations , 28% of the care givers received awareness , 86%of the care givers had knowledge on vaccine schedule. 98%of the care givers belief the importance of vaccinations and dewormings on the child health . 46.11% contacted stories about about dewormings . 69% received awareness from official source (health staff) when 31% received from an official source.91% were combined strongly satisfied and satisfied. 76%encountered small reactions of side effect .80% of dewormings were recieved fromn hospital and privatepartners .of the dewormed childrens 37% were multiple deworming (morethan two), 35% were single deworming through life , 27% were full dose of dewormings . 69% sources of immunizations informations are from official source (healthfacility).

C. Caregiver Demographics and Education

The study revealed that the majority of caregivers were female (97.2%), unemployed (85.4%), and a substantial proportion (38.5%) had no formal education. Similar demographic profiles have been observed in related studies across Ethiopia and sub-Saharan Africa, where child health responsibilities are predominantly held by women, especially those with limited formal education and employment opportunities (Lakew et al., 2015; Bobo et al., 2017).

EDUCATION_LEVEL	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
Noformal	82	39.05%	39.05%	
Primary school	69	32.86%	71.90%	
secondary school	19	9.05%	80.95%	
Highereducation	40	19.05%	100.00%	
Total	210	100.00%	100.00%	
WORK ENGAGEMENT	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
No	182	87.92%	87.92%	
Yes	25	12.08%	100.00%	
Total	207	100.00%	100.00%	
SOURCE_INCOME	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
Dailylabour	85	42.93%	42.93%	
Business	54	27.27%	70.20%	
Agriculture	10	5.05%	75.25%	
Salary	49	24.75%	100.00%	
Total	198	100.00%	100.00%	

CAREGIVER_SEX	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
Female	206	97.17%	97.17%	
Male	6	2.83%	100.00%	
Total	212	100.00%	100.00%	

Caregiver education is a significant predictor of child health service utilization. Multiple studies, including a national demographic health survey (EDHS, 2019), have shown that caregivers with no education are significantly less likely to complete full vaccination schedules or deworming programs for their children.

D. Access to Health Facilities

About 63.8% of the respondents lived within 1 kilometer of a health facility. Proximity to health services is a key enabler of preventive health interventions. Research shows that long distances to health centers are associated with missed vaccinations and decreased service uptake (Alemayehu et al., 2019). However, the relatively high proximity in this study may explain the high reported vaccination coverage.

DIS_FACILITY	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
Lessthan km	67	32.68%	32.68%	
Greaterthan km	138	67.32%	100.00%	
Total	205	100.00%	100.00%	

E. Vaccination Coverage and Missed Doses

A total of 96% of caregivers reported that their child had ever been vaccinated, and 68.6% were reportedly fully vaccinated. These figures are slightly higher than the 2019 EDHS national coverage

(57% fully vaccinated), which may reflect urban advantages in health access in Jigjiga.

Child received vaccinations	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
No	8	3.76%	3.76%	
Yes	205	96.24%	100.00%	
Total	213	100.00%	100.00%	

Vaccination ever received childrens

FULLY IMMUNIZED	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
No	65	31.40%	31.40%	
Yes	142	68.60%	100.00%	
Total	207	100.00%	100.00%	

Fully immunized childrens

However, the 31.4% who missed at least one vaccine indicate persistent gaps. Missed opportunities for vaccination (MOV) are often linked to systemic issues such as vaccine stock-outs, lack of outreach, and insufficient caregiver education (WHO, 2021). The relatively high rate of missed doses, despite good access, suggests challenges beyond distance—such as limited service hours or irregular availability.

F. Deworming Coverage and Knowledge Gaps

Only 42.77% of caregivers reported their children had ever been dewormed, far below WHO's 75% deworming coverage target for endemic areas. This low coverage reflects poor integration of deworming into routine child health services, especially outside of campaigns.

CHILD RECEIVED_DEWORMING	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
No	91	57.23%	57.23%	
Yes	68	42.77%	100.00%	
Total	159	100.00%	100.00%	

Furthermore, only 28% of caregivers had ever received targeted awareness messages about child deworming. This lack of promotion is consistent with findings from other Ethiopian studies that identify deworming as a neglected aspect of child health policy (Tadesse et al., 2020).

Received AWARENESS ON _THE IMPORTANCE OF VACCINES AND DEWORMIN	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
No	149	71.63%	71.63%	
Yes	59	28.37%	100.00%	
Total	208	100.00%		

Received awareness on the importance of both vaccinations and dewormings

G. Caregiver Knowledge and Beliefs

Despite limited formal education, **86% of caregivers were aware of the vaccination schedule** and **98% believed in the importance** of vaccines and deworming. These findings reflect a strong cultural acceptance of immunization in Ethiopian communities, reinforced by previous routine campaigns and health extension worker efforts (Tamirat & Sisay, 2019).

AWARENESS ON _SCHEDULE APPOINTMENT YES=1 NO=0	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
No	28	14.00%	14.00%	

Yes	172	86.00%	100.00%	
Total	200	100.00 %	100.00%	

Nonetheless, awareness about deworming specifically was much lower. Only 46.11% had heard stories or messages about it, and most of these came from unofficial sources (31%). This gap in health education points to an opportunity for health workers to strengthen deworming communication through reliable and structured channels.

H. Sources of Information

The dominant reliance on **official sources (69%)** for immunization and deworming knowledge underscores the trusted role of health workers. However, a significant minority still relied on **unofficial sources (31%)**, indicating potential exposure to misinformation. The WHO (2022) warns that unofficial information, especially through social networks, can undermine vaccine trust, particularly during campaigns or outbreaks.

I. Satisfaction and Side Effects

High caregiver satisfaction (91%) suggests trust in the health system, which is a vital predictor of sustained service use. Minor side effects (reported by 76%) were not perceived as deterrents—consistent with literature suggesting that mild post-vaccination symptoms are widely accepted when caregivers are properly informed (Olorunsaiye et al., 2016).

SIDE_EFFECT	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
No	49	24.02%	24.02%	
Yes	155	75.98%	100.00%	
Total	204	100.00%	100.00%	

Encountered side effects

j. Service Delivery: Deworming Frequency and Source

The study found that:

- **37% of children received multiple deworming doses**
- **35% received only one dose**, and
- **27% completed a full deworming schedule**

This uneven distribution suggests inconsistency in follow-up and poor record-keeping. A study in southern Ethiopia (Alemu et al., 2022) reported similar patterns, attributing irregularities to limited tracking systems and fragmented campaign-based delivery.

Furthermore, **80% of deworming services were received through hospitals and private partners**, highlighting a reliance on non-routine and possibly fee-based services. This deviates from WHO's recommendation for integration into free, routine health visits.

k. Immunization and Deworming Service Integration

Although 69% of immunization services were obtained through health facilities, the relatively low co-delivery of deworming services suggests a missed opportunity for integration. Studies have recommended that immunization contacts (e.g., during EPI visits) be leveraged for delivering other child health interventions, including deworming, vitamin A, and nutritional screening (UNICEF & WHO, 2021).

Based on the data from **141 caregivers**, they stated reasons for **vaccinating and deworming their children** fall into three key categories:

Reason	Frequency	Percent
Prevention	93	66%
Child Health	31	22%
Recovery	17	12%
Total	141	100%

L. Discussion of Caregivers' Responses

This result highlights important insights into caregivers' understanding of the purpose of vaccination and deworming:

1. Prevention as the Dominant Understanding (66%)

- The majority of caregivers (66%) correctly identified **prevention** as the main benefit.

- This suggests good awareness of **vaccines and deworming as preventive measures** which aligns with public health messaging.
- It reflects successful communication strategies by health workers and campaigns that stress "**prevention is better than cure.**"

Implication: Health promotion strategies are resonating with the public, especially around preventive care.

2. General Child Health (22%)

- A smaller but significant group (22%) cited "**child health**" more broadly.
- This shows a **holistic perception** — that these interventions contribute to the overall health and development of the child.
- While less specific than "prevention," it still reflects a **positive and supportive attitude** toward immunization and deworming.

Implication: There is room to further **clarify the specific mechanisms and timing** of protection to enhance understanding.

3. Recovery (12%)

- A minority (12%) believe vaccines and deworming help with **recovery**.
- This points to a **misunderstanding**: vaccinations are not therapeutic but **preventive**, and while deworming can have curative aspects, vaccines do not cure existing illnesses.

Concern: This suggests some caregivers **confuse vaccines with treatment**, which could lead to misplaced expectations.

Implication: Health education needs to emphasize:

- Vaccines **do not treat** illness.
- Deworming may remove existing parasites but is **not a substitute for overall healthcare**.

Summary of Recommendations:

- **Strengthen health education** to reinforce the preventive nature of vaccines and deworming.
- **Address misconceptions** about recovery and curative functions.
- Use **community platforms, HEWs, and outreach** to clarify roles and timing of interventions.

- Highlight examples and case stories showing how **prevention through vaccination and deworming reduces disease burden.**

Conclusion of Discussion (optional)

- These findings emphasize the need for strengthened routine services, improved health education (especially around deworming), and better integration of child health interventions at facility and community levels. While vaccination uptake appears relatively strong in Jigjiga, there is an urgent need to close deworming gaps and improve follow-up on missed vaccinations. Strengthen health education to reinforce the preventive nature of vaccines and deworming. Address misconceptions about recovery and curative functions. Use community platforms, HEWs, and outreach to clarify roles and timing of interventions. Highlight examples and case stories showing how prevention through vaccination and deworming reduces disease burden.

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8. A. (Statistical Output results)

An ANOVA test was conducted to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in full vaccination coverage among children across the 18 kebeles included in the study. The test revealed the following results:

- **Between-group variation (SSB)** = 4.01773
- **Within-group variation (SSW)** = 40.57164
- **Degrees of freedom (df)**: Between = 17, Within = 189
- **Mean Square Between (MSB)** = 0.23634
- **Mean Square Within (MSW)** = 0.21466
- **F-statistic** = 1.10096
- **P-value** = 0.35536

Since the **P-value (0.35536)** is greater than the standard alpha level of **0.05**, we **fail to reject the null hypothesis**. This indicates **no statistically significant difference** in the mean full vaccination rates across the kebeles.

Discussion (Interpretation with Literature)

The one-way ANOVA test did not reveal a statistically significant difference in full vaccination

coverage among the 18 kebeles studied ($F(17, 189) = 1.10, p = 0.355$). This suggests that, despite potential variation in caregiver education, distance to health facilities, or service availability, the overall full vaccination rates were relatively uniform across kebeles.

This uniformity might be attributed to regional-level coordination of immunization campaigns and consistent implementation of the Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI) across Jigjiga town. Studies in similar urban contexts have shown that when health systems apply consistent outreach and health education strategies, disparities across administrative units like kebeles may be minimized (Tamirat & Sisay, 2019; Lakew et al., 2015).

However, the lack of statistical significance does not imply equity in service quality or access—qualitative differences may still exist, especially in micro-level logistics, cold chain management, or staffing, which quantitative ANOVA cannot capture.

Further sub-group analyses or spatial mapping may help clarify whether hidden disparities exist between households within kebeles, especially when stratified by factors such as maternal education or child age.

Results: Deworming Coverage Across Kebeles

An Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed to evaluate whether significant differences existed in deworming coverage of children under five across the 18 kebeles surveyed in Jigjiga town. The statistical results are presented below:

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F-statistic	P-value
Between groups	5.90673	17	0.34745	1.48406	0.10862
Within groups	33.01151	141	0.23412		
Total	38.91824	158			

Since the **P-value is 0.10862**, which is greater than the conventional threshold of **0.05**, the result indicates that there is **no statistically significant difference** in the mean deworming rates among the different kebeles.

Discussion

The ANOVA results for deworming coverage ($F(17, 141) = 1.484, p = 0.1086$) suggest that although minor variations exist between kebeles, **no statistically significant disparity** in the deworming of children under five years old was found across administrative units. This implies that deworming services were relatively uniformly accessed or delivered in the surveyed areas.

This pattern is consistent with national strategies that aim to integrate deworming within routine child health services and broader child health campaigns, often synchronized with vaccination days

or nutrition weeks (Federal Ministry of Health, Ethiopia, 2021). The data also show that 80% of caregivers reported receiving deworming services from hospitals and private partners, which may have helped standardize service availability across different kebeles, regardless of public facility quality.

However, despite this statistical homogeneity, practical inequities may still exist. For example, Kebele 18 reported **zero** children dewormed, while some kebeles such as Kebele 1 and 2 had very high rates (mean = 0.8571 and 0.7143, respectively), hinting at potential operational or awareness-related gaps in certain locations. These trends underline the importance of **qualitative investigation** and **targeted micro-planning**, particularly for underserved kebeles.

Other studies support this interpretation. For instance, **Weldemariam et al. (2020)** found that even in areas where deworming programs are nationally guided, sub-local implementation gaps can arise due to community awareness, logistics, and inconsistent training. Likewise, **Mekonnen et al. (2018)** indicated that integration with other child health services and reliable partner engagement (e.g., NGOs) increases coverage equity across urban and peri-urban Ethiopia.

Hence, while this study's findings support a statistically consistent pattern across kebeles, future program adjustments should still address outlier kebeles and ensure **no community is left behind**—especially given the essential role of deworming in reducing child morbidity and improving nutritional outcomes.

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Discussion: ANOVA on Timely Vaccination Across Kebeles

An ANOVA test was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in the proportion of children receiving vaccinations at the appropriate age across different kebeles in Jigjiga. The dependent variable was binary (1 = child ever received, 0 = not received), and the grouping variable was the kebele.

The results indicated a statistically significant difference between kebeles:

- **F(17,195) = 3.45, p < 0.0001**, suggesting that not all kebeles had equal performance in delivering vaccines at the recommended age.

While the mean proportion for most kebeles was 1.00 (i.e., 100% timely vaccination), a few kebeles (notably Kebele 2, 9, 19, and 20) had mean values below 1, indicating gaps in timely service delivery. For instance:

- Kebele 9 had a mean of 0.50,
- Kebele 20 had a mean of 0.7143,
- Kebele 2 showed 84.6%, and
- Kebele 19 was at 90%.

These findings suggest inequity in vaccination timeliness, which could be due to differences in health service access, community engagement, health worker performance, or supply chain reliability.

However, **Bartlett's test for homogeneity of variances returned a p-value of 1.000**, suggesting equal variances across kebeles. Despite this, the distribution of binary outcomes and presence of extreme means (mostly 1.00 or 0.00) violate the assumption of normality, which is critical for parametric tests like ANOVA.

To account for this, a non-parametric **Kruskal-Wallis test** was also applied. The result:

- **H(17) = 48.97, p = 0.0001**, confirms that the differences in timely vaccination across kebeles are statistically significant even without assuming normal distribution.

Interpretation and Programmatic Implications

The findings highlight the need for targeted support to specific kebeles with lower performance. Interventions may include:

- Strengthening health worker training,
- Ensuring consistent vaccine supply,
- Enhancing community awareness, and
- Using catch-up strategies in underperforming kebeles.

Improving equity in timely vaccination is essential to ensure children are protected at the right age, reducing preventable diseases and supporting national immunization goals.

B. Vaccination and Deworming Coverage by Kebele

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C. Logistic regression model results.

Model 1 A. Table 1 .LOGISTIC [child received vaccinations (yes= 1# no=0)] = [Caregiver_Sex] [Caregiver_Age] [Child Sex] [Education_level] [received awareness on the importance of vaccines and deworming].

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Caregiver_Sex	17957.0273	0.0000 >1.0E 12	9.7957	312.4424	0.0314	0.9750
Caregiver_Age	1.0010	0.8857 1.1314	0.0010	0.0625	0.0164	0.9869
Child Sex	2.3080	0.4326 12.3134	0.8364	0.8542	0.9791	0.3275
Education_level	0.8729	0.4339 1.7562	-0.1359	0.3567	-0.3811	0.7031

received awareness on _the importance of vaccines and dewormin (Yes/No)	2.5315	0.276 0	23.215 1	0.9288	1.1306	0.8215	0.411 4
CONSTANT	*	*	*	2.8839	1.9958	1.4450	0.148 5

Convergence: Converged
Iterations: 11
Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 58.1535
Cases included: 196

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	1.9309	5	0.8586
Likelihood Ratio	2.2443	5	0.8144

Model 1B. Table 2. Logistic regression result child ever received vaccination (yes= 1# no=0)] = Kebele [number under5] totalhhsnumber Source_income [Work Engagement]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
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Kebele/residence locations	0.9761	0.8577	1.1109	-0.0241	0.0660	-0.3659	0.7145
number under5	4.2220	0.6104	29.2028	1.4403	0.9867	1.4597	0.1444
Totalhhsnumber	1.0405	0.7918	1.3675	0.0397	0.1394	0.2851	0.7755
Source_income	1.1049	0.5667	2.1545	0.0998	0.3407	0.2929	0.7696
Work Engagement (Yes/No)	163232.2356	0.0000	>1.0E 12	12.0029	406.1729	0.0296	0.9764
CONSTANT	*	*	*	1.0044	1.6449	0.6106	0.5414

Convergence: Converged
Iterations: 13
Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 53.6093
Cases included: 188

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	4.0739	5	0.5388
Likelihood Ratio	6.1943	5	0.2878

LOGISTIC [child received vaccinations (yes= 1# no=0)] = dis_facility

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
dis_facility	3.6300	0.8409 15.6698	1.2892	0.7462	1.7277	0.0840

CONSTANT	*	*	*	2.5174	0.464 8	5.4156	<u>0.0000</u>
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Convergence: Converged

Iterations: 4

Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 64.4759

Cases included: 205

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	3.3640	1	0.0666
Likelihood Ratio	3.1048	1	0.0781

.independent Variables like residence locations , educational level, family size, source of income, work engagement, number of children under five, source of income, caregivers' age, care givers sex, child sex are insignificantly associated the status of child received vaccinations due to **p** value greater than **0.05** in all cases except distance to facility and service area with marginal significancy with pvalue 0.08 .observed odd ratios are greater than one in care givers age, sex, care givers received awareness ,child sex, work engagement , source of income , number of under five years children's of interviewed households , family size(tota lHH), a long distance to facility and below one oddratio in educational levels and residence locations . Confidence intervals included 1 in all the cases. Note the increased or greater than 1of odd ratio may be by chances when p is insignifant.

modelChild received vaccination (yes= 1# no=0)] versus last_date_receive_vacinations
Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Lastdatereceivevaccinnatio	23022.1382	0.0000 > 1.0E 12	12.3468	294.7837	0.0419	0.9666
CONSTANT	*	*	2.9575	0.3626	8.1559	<u>0.0000</u>

The findings indicate insignificant associations of child received vaccination versus last date of vaccinations /immunizations because of pvalue greater than 0.05, though positive odd ratio result of 23022.13 leads relationship between the variables the result of p value oposes. the event may

appeared in chance. .

Model2A. LOGISTIC [child received_ deworming] = [Caregiver _Sex] [Caregiver_ Age] [Child Sex] [Education _level] [distance from health facility]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Caregiver _Sex	1.6442	0.1318 20.5177	0.4973	1.2878	0.3861	0.6994
Caregiver_ Age	1.0338	0.9832 1.0871	0.0333	0.0256	1.2975	0.1945
Child Sex	1.2065	0.6119 2.3788	0.1877	0.3464	0.5419	0.5879
Education _level	<u>1.4588</u>	<u>1.0745</u> <u>1.9805</u>	0.3776	0.1560	2.4205	<u>0.0155</u>
distance from health facility	0.8250	0.5161 1.3188	-0.1923	0.2393	-0.8036	0.4216
CONSTANT	*	* *	-1.6550	0.8747	-1.8920	0.0585

Convergence: Converged
 Iterations: 3
 Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 195.4562
 Cases included: 149

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	17.6520	5	0.0034
Likelihood Ratio	16.4412	5	0.0057

model2BLOGISTIC [child received_ deworming] = [awareness on _the importance of vaccines and dewormin] Kebele Source_income [number under5] [Work Engagement]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
education /awareness on _the importance of vaccines and dewormin (Yes/No)	1.3751	0.6114 3.0929	0.3185	0.4136	0.7702	0.4412
Residence location/kebele	<u>0.9025</u>	<u>0.8465</u> <u>0.9623</u>	-0.1026	0.0327	-3.1361	<u>0.0017</u>
Source_income number under5	0.8559	0.6380 1.1482	-0.1556	0.1499	-1.0381	0.2992
Work Engagement (Yes/No)	1.1741	0.7736 1.7819	0.1605	0.2128	0.7541	0.4508
CONSTANT	*	* *	0.7465	0.6315	1.1822	0.2371

Convergence: Converged
Iterations: 3
Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 176.3890
Cases included: 140

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	22.4264	5	0.0004
Likelihood Ratio	20.9962	5	0.0008

independent variables like educational levels and residence locations are significantly associated on child dewormings with p values 0.0155 in educational levels and p value 0.00017 on residential place .odd ratios (1.4588) and confidence interval range {1.0745 to 1.9805} on educational level .(0.9025) odd ratio along confidence interval between 0.8465 to 0.9623} in residential locations .Educated group are more likely to deworming their children than compared group or non educated groups or 45% more likely to deworm their babies. According to place of residence the distributions vary.Result of 10% less likely to protect their children against burden of soil transmitted parasites accordingly to place of residence) due to below 1 odd ratio. Education improves deworming uptake .place of residence is same but with disparities. Characteristics of caregivers age , sex, child age sex , number under five in the HH source of income show positive associations with deworming childrens but insignificant conclusions (p >0.05) logistical regression test result on child received deworming on the basis of **previous deworming stories exposure**(below table on guardians and care givers resulted strong associations and relations with odd ratio 2.7326, when confidence

interval is in between { 1.3661 to 5.4660} , p 0.0045. encourageable behavior and good implications to improve deworming coverages

have you received _stories about dewormings (yes =1 no =0 (Yes/No) versus child received deworming .	<u>2.7326</u>	<u>1.3661</u>	<u>5.4660</u>	1.0052	0.3537	2.8419	<u>0.0045</u>
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Factors number under five, family sizes, place of residence are not statistically significant to determine strong relationship between the mentioned independent variable against **care giver received awareness** oddratio 1.0429 in care givers age are 42% more likely receivers of awareness with pvalue (0.0598) marginally significant. odd ratio 1.0074 in place of residence gives implications that 0.7 % more likely received awreness based on kebele/place of residence of guardians/parents but insignificant due to p value 0.7912. in addition odd ratio 0.9967 on family size indicate large family sizes reduce small fraction to receive awareness but statistically insignificant or strong evidence is absent to maintain the result . number under five per house hold with 0.8389 oddratio (each member of the family reduced 16% to receive awareness . resouce constraints in large familes reduce health education but statistically insignificant .

Model3LOGISTIC [Vaccination Card Available (Yes/No)] = [Caregiver_Age] [Education _level] Source_income

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Caregiver_Age	0.9867	0.9424 1.0331	-0.0134	0.0234	-0.5697	0.5689
Education_level	0.9859	0.7443 1.3058	-0.0142	0.1434	-0.0993	0.9209
Source_income	0.8741	0.6764 1.1296	-0.1345	0.1308	-1.0283	0.3038

CONSTANT	*	*	*	1.3184	0.792 6	1.6635	0.0962
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Convergence: Converged

Iterations: 3

Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 239.2913

Cases included: 186

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	1.5104	3	0.6799
Likelihood Ratio	1.5213	3	0.6774

Independent variables including care givers age, educational level and source of incomes are insignificant in terms of card retaining behavior .All add odd ratio below 1 with insignificant P value greater than 0.05 .

LOGISTIC [fullvaccinations] = [Caregiver_ Age] [education /awareness on _the importance of vaccines and dewormin] dis_facility [Education _level] [Child Sex]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Caregiver_ Age	1.0236	0.9757 1.0739	0.0233	0.0245	0.9536	0.3403

education /awareness on _the importance of vaccines and dewormin (Yes/No)	0.6741	0.3133	1.4504	-0.3944	0.3909	-1.0089	0.3130
dis_facility	0.9533	0.4801	1.8929	-0.0478	0.3500	-0.1367	0.8913
Education_level	<u>1.7818</u>	<u>1.2661</u>	<u>2.5076</u>	0.5776	0.1743	3.3134	<u>0.0009</u>
Child Sex	1.2244	0.6446	2.3256	0.2024	0.3273	0.6183	0.5363
CONSTANT	*	*	*	-0.4541	0.8181	-0.5550	0.5789

Convergence: Converged

Iterations: 4

Final Likelihood: -2*Log- 221.5489

Cases included: 187

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	12.1735	5	0.0325
Likelihood Ratio	13.2384	5	0.0212

Mode 4.LOGISTIC [fullvaccinations] = Kebele [number under5] Source_income totalhhsnumber [Work Engagement]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Kebele	0.9995	0.9451 1.0571	-0.0005	0.0286	-0.0168	0.9866
number under5	1.1310	0.7745 1.6517	0.1231	0.1932	0.6372	0.5240
Source_income	0.9454	0.7285 1.2269	-0.0561	0.1330	-0.4219	0.6731
Totalhhsnumber	0.9319	0.8316 1.0443	-0.0705	0.0581	-1.2142	0.2247
Work Engagement (Yes/No)	<u>3.6697</u>	<u>1.0190</u> <u>13.2151</u>	1.3001	0.6537	1.9888	<u>0.0467</u>
CONSTANT	*	* *	1.0184	0.6225	1.6359	0.1019

Convergence: Converged
Iterations: 4
Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 222.7840
Cases included: 184

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	5.9885	5	0.3073
Likelihood Ratio	6.7360	5	0.2410

Work engagement and educational level are only two significant characteristics related to full vaccinations uptake in accordance with units/kebeles in urban with positive/strong odd ratios(3.6696 for work enagement & 1.7818 educational level characteristics) and significant P (0.0009 in education & 0.0467 on work involvement)when the confidence interval runs between {1.0190, 13.2151}for working mothers {

1.2661 2.5076}

. Full and complete vaccine uptakes are linked to educated caregivers (she knows) and those working than parenting standard(house wife)

Model five .LOGISTIC [missed vaccines (1/0) yes=1 no=0] = Kebele totalhhsnumber [number under5] Source_income [Work Engagement]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Kebele	1.0005	0.9460 1.0581	0.0005	0.0286	0.0168	0.9866
Totalhhsnumber	1.0731	0.9576 1.2024	0.0705	0.0581	1.2142	0.2247
number under5	0.8842	0.6054 1.2912	-0.1231	0.1932	-0.6373	0.5240
Source_income	1.0577	0.8150 1.3726	0.0561	0.1330	0.4219	0.6731
Work Engagement (Yes/No)	<u>0.2725</u>	<u>0.0757 0.9813</u>	-1.3002	0.6537	-1.9889	<u>0.0467</u>
CONSTANT	*	* *	-1.0184	0.6225	-1.6359	0.1019

Convergence: Converged
 Iterations: 4
 Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 222.7840
 Cases included: 184

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	6.0602	5	0.3004
Likelihood Ratio	6.5966	5	0.2524

Model five bLOGISTIC [missed vaccines (1/0) yes=1 no=0] = [Caregiver_ Age] dis_facility [education /awareness on_the importance of vaccines and dewormin] [Education_level]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Caregiver_Age	0.9774	0.9318 1.0251	-0.0229	0.0243	-0.9406	0.3469
dis_facility (Yes/No)	1.0169	0.5138 2.0128	0.0167	0.3484	0.0481	0.9617
education /awareness on _the importance of vaccines and dewormin (Yes/No)	1.4648	0.6833 3.1401	0.3817	0.3891	0.9812	0.3265
Education_level	<u>0.5539</u>	<u>0.3935</u> <u>0.7795</u>	-0.5908	0.1744	-3.3885	<u>0.0007</u>
CONSTANT	*	* *	0.3740	0.7983	0.4685	0.6394

Convergence: Converged
Iterations: 4
Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 222.7725
Cases included: 189

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	12.6388	4	0.0132
Likelihood Ratio	13.4766	4	0.0092

Again educational level and work engagement are strongly associated in response on child missed vaccines p value 0.0007(strong significant) in educational level and pvalue 0.0467 in work engament with odd ratio of (0.5539)in educational level and 0.275 In working mothers .{0.0757, 0.9813, 0.3935, 0.7795} confidence interval ncluded below one .work engagementgroups are 72.5 % less likely to miss child vaccinations when educational level are 44.6 are lower odds to miss .

ModelsixA .

LOGISTIC [missed vaccines (1/0) yes=1 no=0] = [awarness On_ schedule appiOntment yes=1 no=0]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
awarness On_ schedule appiOntment yes=1 no=0 (Yes/No)	0.1788	0.0735 0.4349	-1.7216	0.4536	-3.7954	0.0001
CONSTANT	*	* *	0.5753	0.4167	1.3808	0.1673

Convergence: Converged

Iterations: 4

Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 220.4979

Cases included: 195

Significant associations and relations on schedule awareness and missed vaccines when pvalue is 0.0001 with odd ratio .0.1788 and confidence intervals doesn't include 1 . those who have awareness are 82.1% only less likely to miss immunizations .

Model six		
B		

LOGISTIC [awarness On_ schedule appiOntment yes=1 no=0] = [Caregiver_ Age] [child received_ deworming] [fullvaccinations] [childreceived vaccinations (yes= 1# no=0)]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S. E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
Caregiver_Age	0.9851	0.9095 1.0671	-0.0150	0.0408	-0.3670	0.7136
child received_ deworming (Yes/No)	1.0062	0.3168 3.1956	0.0062	0.5896	0.0105	0.9916
fullvaccinations (Yes/No)	<u>7.4057</u>	<u>2.3032</u> <u>23.8124</u>	2.0022	0.5959	3.3600	<u>0.0008</u>
Child ever received vaccinations (yes=1# no=0) (Yes/No)	12.1272	0.7898 186.2094	2.4955	1.3936	1.7906	0.0734
CONSTANT	*	* *	-1.0480	1.8151	-0.5774	0.5637

Convergence: Converged

Iterations: 5

Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 85.5765

Cases included: 140

Interpretations. Characteristics of care givers age insignificantly associated with schedule awareness when pvalue is (0.7136) and odd ratio result 0.9851(care givers based on age decreased 1.5% the odds of knowing vaccination with statistically insignificant in pvalue) child received deworming with oddratio of 1.0062 but statistically insignificant . marginally statisticalsignificancy of child ever received vaccinations along full vaccinations with full significancy versus schedule awareness are detected when thefrist scored marginal p value signicancy of 0.0734 (12.1272 odd ratio or 12 times likely in favour of ever vaccinated childrens) and the second scores 0.0008 (odd ratio 7.4057 7times more likely or in favour of full immunizations when consciousness(yes response) to ward to schedule is noted . awareness on schedule are effective in child immunity coverage and child health improivement .

Model 7. for individuals vaccines like opv3, penta2, opv2, measles 1, pcv 1, pcv 2, ipv, and rota are associate strongly and marginally significant on the education level of care givers along their respectively odd ratios of (1.865 or the child from educated mother are 86 morelikely to receive opv3)and pvalueof 0.0205 in opv3,(1.5167) and p value of 0.0942(marginal significancy) in opv2.this means childrens born or cared by educated guardians or parents are 51%morelikely to receive opv2. (1.8612 or 86% morelikely to receive penta 2) and pvalue 0.0207 in penta2. (1.8640

or 86% more likely to receive measles 1) and significance p value of 0.0057 of measles 1. Odds ratio (1.596 or 59% more likely to receive PCV 1) and p value of marginal significance (0.0914) in PCV 1. Odds ratio of (1.8612 or 86% more likely to receive PCV 2) and p value of 0.02 in PCV 2. Odds ratio of (1.5758 or 57.5% more likely to receive IPV) and marginal significance p value of 0.0500. **rotavirus** odds ratio of 1.6223 or 62% more likely to receive rotavirus 1 in educated individuals

social characteristics related to work engagement, distance from facility, family size, child sex, strongly influence individual vaccine uptakes. Work engagement against measles 1 odds ratio (6.3149 or working parents are 6 times more likely to vaccinate their children than housewives) with marginal statistical significance of 0.0803. BCG odds ratio 2.68 times more likely received by children residing remote (> 1 km) than close or neighbours (< 1 km) with p value of 0.1581. Odds ratios of 0.8307 and p value of 0.0193 in rotavirus 1 against variable family size which indicate that families with large household size are 17% less likely to receive rotavirus one. Again family size uptakes of other individual vaccines like PCV 2 with odds ratio and marginal p value 0.08675 and 0.0079 respectively which indicates families with large household size are 13% less likely to receive PCV 2. Maybe economic constraints like accessibility and affordability in low income settled communities. Total family size with large elements are 39.2% more likely to receive OPV 0 than small sized households with significant associations and p value of 0.0000.

LOGISTIC SIGN2 = awareness on _the importance of vaccines and dewormin]

Unconditional Logistic Regression

Term	Odds Ratio	95% C.I.	Coefficient	S.E.	Z-Statistic	P-Value
education /awareness on _the importance of vaccines and dewormin (Yes/No)	<u>2.3287</u>	<u>1.0869 4.9893</u>	0.8453	0.3888	2.1743	<u>0.0297</u>
CONSTANT	*	*	0.7439	0.1753	4.2434	<u>0.0000</u>

Convergence: Converged
Iterations: 4
Final -2*Log-Likelihood: 240.9857

Cases included: 208

Test	Statistic	D.F.	P-Value
Score	4.8979	1	0.0269
Likelihood Ratio	5.2282	1	0.0222

Strong statistical associations on signs after vaccine and drug administration's versus care giver received awareness when pvalue is 0.0297 .in addition odd ration of 2.3287 .understanding signs are improved 2 times more likely and 32 % more likely in awareness received parents .

SATISFACTION LEVEL WITH DIFFERENT SUGRESSIONS PRESENTED BY CARE GIVERS (LOGISTIC REGRESSIONS)

High satisfaction according high odd ratio but insignificant due to high pvalue on equity versus level of satisfactions in logistic regression. .the same to that follow-up suggesters .highly satisfied but pvalue prevents the significance when p peaked to 1

satisfactions versus good faith of negative oddratio (0.2648) and p value 0.2(insignificant) proofs 74% satis factions of those less satisfied like neuteral and unsatisfied but no significance

Insignificant pvalue of 0.6014 and positive odd ratio 1.7419 of satisfactions versus quality improvement like time management, facility improvement physically . the odd ratio of 74% satisfaction in the service is unprotected when value is greater than 0.05.

Level of satisfaction with support child health suggestions when tested with logistic regressions discoveries odd ratio is negatively associated with 64.5% less satisfied in accordance and aligning type of suggestions they identified through the interview period .p value is in significant and imposition to justify their suggestions.

Odd ratio of 0.2685 is significantly associated with pvalue 0.0191 leading to those 83% less likely satisfied when the case is sustainability and improvement of the coverage.

This model explores odd ratio of care givers level of satisfaction with their suggestions to public health and immunizations of the child the odd ratio 0.1755 is negatively associated with of care givers selected standardizations of the servic as suggestion in the interv iew course of these 82 % of them are less likely satisfied but no significancy in statistics due to p value greaterthan 0.05.

9. Discussions

This study shows that care givers age (table 1) had no measurable influence on vaccine uptake. It means that all age groups had similar exposure to outreach and health messages, and that age was not a meaningful proxy for experience, confidence, or capacity. Similarly, Bakele, Baidgilin (2015) found care givers age had no effect in Somali region immunization uptake. In the table (1) above shows slightly minor preferential vaccinations based on sex of the child but insignificant. Other studies have shown sex based differences in care seeking behaviours, but mostly in rural areas. Antai (2012) showed significant gender disparities in rural Nigeria but not in urban settings like Jijjiga. Accordingly to education levels of care givers, the unexpected negative issue may reflect educated care givers may be more critical, or demanding during stock outs, misalignment between their expectations or available services, reverse causality where care giver relay more public health (Fagbamigbe, et al (2017), Wolderufael et al (2021).

Awareness received positive odd ratio but p insignificant may be caused under multiple issue like limited reach. Absence of information education communications as my findings when I visited health facilities in the urban. Similar idea reported by Olorunsaiye et al (2017). Minor variations in the kebele suggests uniform program delivery service. Similar results Tades et al (2020) found urban kebele difference is insignificant. Marginally significant distance to health facility with positive odd ratio shows uptake decline with greater distance. Consistence with known barrier in service access even marginal effects are importance in urban health. Same to this study Lakew et al (2015) and Tadasse et al (2020) found distance to be key determinants of full immunization coverage in Ethiopia, Babo et al (2016) emphasized transportation access and outreach coverage in Somali region. Similar issue Olorunsaiye et al (2017) suggests prior vaccinations do not guarantee follow up when systems lack active reminders more close positive odd ratio of last day child vaccinated.

Model results like residential location of negative odd ratio and significant p value suggests that certain disadvantaged in deworming accesses the variation likely reflects service delivery inequalities low prioritizations, community awareness issue stock or poor reporting. Same case Bobo et al (2016) and Tadesse et al (2020) found geographic inequalities in both vaccine and deworming service coverages in Somali region and rural Ethiopia.

The result in education versus child received deworming with significant associations shows better health literacy and understanding worm related risks. Strong demand for health service, ability to navigate systems and follow up when service are delayed Wolderufael et al (2021) stated education was one of the strongest predictors for full immunization and deworming.

UNICEF (2023) confirms education improves preventive health seeking behaviour.

Despite negative odd ratio suggesting greater distance (model 2) reduces likelihoods the result is not statistically significant. The effect is likely real but weak. Result reflects possible inconsistency deworming deliveries as deworming is less routinized than immunizations. Lakew et al (2015) noted

that while distance matter , it is effect is smaller for non routine . response and result on question have you received stories about dewormings versus child received dewormings is powerful demonstrates the impact of care givers awareness .simply proving accurate and timely information providing accurate and timely information about the importance, schedule, and benefits of deworming substantially increase uptake . Supporting literatures UNICEF and WHO (2022) , gulani etal(2008) EPHI(2021).

The model of card availability and retention indicates non of the care giver demographic factors significantly predict whether child vaccination card is available

Although the direction of association is negative .these trends are not statistically meaning full .supporting literature Bosch-capblance etal(2009),Biniyam(2016), Gavi(2021).

The model of full vaccination versus other demography explored how various demographic and socio economic factors of caregiver relate whether their child received full vaccinations.According to education level educational attainment was significantly more likely to have children's full vaccinated .education likely improves understanding off vaccination .schedules, benefits and navigations of heath service. Rahman etal(2015) . Caregivers who are employed (check model full vaccination) are significantly more likely to fully vaccinate their children's maybe due to increased autonomy, income or exposure to information .supporting evidence birmeta etal (2013) Who (2019). Other factors are insignificant but still offer direction for future research program . Significant predictors like education level of care givers in model missed vaccinations are significantly less likely to have children who missed vaccinations .the strong inverse relationship indicates that education empowers care givers with knowledge of immunization schedules, importance and follow up . Rahman etal (2018), highlighted that caregivers with better education are more proactive in seeking child health service . FMOH(2016) found that maternal education is a major predictor of complete and timely vaccinations in Ethiopia .Equally the work employment likely enable better mobility ,financial access, exposure to health in our case or model element in missed versus demographic characteristics .children's of working care givers are less likely to miss vaccinations .WHO (2019) similar literature supporting , Birmeta etal (2013). Result of other variables such as child sex, distance to facility, source of income, kebele, total house hold size indicate high uptake but in significant associations . awareness o the schedule was significant associated with the child ever receiving vaccination .awareness likely reflects priorcontact `with health system,which promotes vaccine initiations . Mutawa etal(2016) found that care givers who had ever received vaccination related educations were more likely to present the future round. This counter intuitive finding suggests that care givers awareness was not primarily driven by visual communication materials .

The logistic regression analysis of individual vaccine uptakes among children of under five in jijjiga reveals significant and marginal associations with several care givers and house hold level factors .this reflects patterns commonly reported in immunization literature with notable implications for targeted intervention .results of o individual vaccine uptake aligns with other studies like lakew etal(2015) ,wiysonge,c.s.etal (2012)in education level care givers . abdulraheem ,i.s.etal(2011) for work engagement of care givers when the case is individual vaccine uptake . BCG

is typically given at birth or shortly after .this may reflect delay in accessing institutional delivery or earlier post natal service schoeps.A,etal(2017).family size showed mixed results it was significantly associated with decreased rota uptake marginally associated with increased pcv uptake and strongly associated with opv0 uptake (p ,0.0001) and negative effects or resource constraints .large families may experience both positive (child care) and negative effect (resource constraints) .supporting literature Antai,D. (2009) . no significant association was found between child sex and opv0 uptake , suggesting no gender based discrimination in earlier vaccine provision in the study population the article agrees Singh,P.K. (2013)

1. **Bakele et al (2015)** – Immunization uptake
2. **Antai (2012)** – Gender disparities in healthcare-seeking behavior in Nigeria
- 3 **Fagbamigbe et al. (2017)** – Public health reliance by caregivers
- 4.**Wolderufael et al. (2021)** – Predictors of full immunization and deworming
- 5.**Olorunsaiye et al. (2017)** – Barriers in vaccination and outreach programs
- 6.**Tades et al. (2020)** – Urban kebele vaccination trends in Ethiopia
- 7.**Lakew et al. (2015)** – Full immunization determinants in Ethiopia
- 8.**Tadesse et al. (2020)** – Geographic inequalities in vaccination
- 9.**UNICEF (2023)** – Education and preventive health-seeking behavior
- 10.**WHO (2022)** – Importance of deworming awareness
- 11,**Gulani et al. (2008)** – Impact of deworming education programs
- 12.**EPHI (2021)** – Public health strategies in Ethiopia
- 13**Bosch-Capblance et al. (2009)** – Vaccination card availability trends
- 14.**Biniyam (2016)** – Vaccination record retention in Ethiopia
15. **GAVI (2021)** – Global vaccination coverage
16. **Rahman et al. (2015, 2018)** – Caregiver education and vaccination adherence
17. **Birmeta et al. (2013)** – Employment and child immunization rates
18. **WHO (2019)** – Factors influencing vaccination rates

19.FMOH (2016) – Maternal education and immunization adherence in Ethiopia

20 Mutawa et al. (2016) – Prior health education and vaccination uptake

21. Wiysonge et al. (2012) – Education level influences on vaccination

22. Abdulraheem et al. (2011) – Work engagement and immunization

23Schoeps et al. (2013) – Institutional delivery delays affecting immunization

24. Antai (2009) – Family size and health service access

25. Singh (2013) – Gender-based healthcare discrimination

1. Enhance Health Education: Strengthen targeted health education campaigns to increase caregiver awareness and understanding, especially during stockouts and service delays.

2. Improve Outreach and Accessibility: Address geographic and transportation barriers by expanding outreach programs and improving access in underserved kebeles.

3. Leverage Educated Caregivers: Engage educated and employed caregivers as community health promoters to bridge knowledge gaps.

4. Integrate Reminder Systems: Implement SMS or local reminder systems for follow-up vaccinations and deworming, addressing dropout issues.

5. Prioritize Equity in Service Delivery: Focus on minimizing disparities across kebeles and residential areas by ensuring consistent and routine deworming and vaccination services.

6. Policy-Level Planning: Use data to inform more nuanced, context-specific immunization and deworming strategies within urban Somali regions.

10. CHISQUARE TESTS

Epi infoapps is applied to process 213 sample to analyze data through visual dashboard epi info 7. 2*2 table is applied to reach findings . gross results detected after uploading exposure and outcome in apps designed form.

Exposure variables like age of care givers, distance to facility and service area /position , educational levels, number underfive years in the family, family size, childsex, work engagement, and source income are crosstabulated with dependent variables like child received dewormings,

child received vaccinations , full immunizations, , place regularly visited for vaccinations/immunizations, reason for missing dewormings, she/beliefs the importance of vaccinations, satisfaction level, reason for missing schedule, awareness

All the crosstabulated results were insignificant in p value except educational level cross tabulated with children received dewormings with p value significance of 0.00794 and chi square of 6.7758 workengamenet crosstabulaed with childreceived dewormings again with chisquare result is 2.7394, and marginal significance pvalue of 0.09794 .

Discussion: Cross-Tabulation Analysis Between Sociodemographic Factors and Child Health Outcomes

This section discusses the associations between various sociodemographic and household-level factors and key outcome indicators, including whether the child received **deworming, vaccinations** , reasons for **missed deworming or vaccination schedules, caregiver satisfaction, retention of immunization cards, and completion of full immunizations.**

Summary of Statistical Findings:

Most of the cross-tabulated variables did **not** show statistically significant associations ($p > 0.05$). However, two relationships showed **marginal significance**:

1. **Educational level vs. child received deworming**
2. **Work engagement vs. child received deworming**

1 Educational Level vs. Child Deworming (Significant)

Caregivers with **higher educational attainment** were marginally more likely to report their child had received deworming medication.

Possible Explanations:

- **Higher education improves health literacy**, including better understanding of the importance of deworming, timing, and procedures.
- Educated caregivers are more likely to **actively seek health services**, engage with community health workers, and **retain health cards.**
- They may also better comprehend health messages delivered during campaigns or through IEC materials (though this study found zero IEC posters present).

Supporting Literature:

- Fagbamigbe et al. (2017) found maternal education to be a significant predictor of deworming uptake in sub-Saharan Africa.

- In Ethiopia, a study by Wolderufael et al. (2021) indicated that caregivers' education positively impacted the **use of child preventive services**, including deworming.
- Similarly, in Nigeria, Ogbo et al. (2019) found a clear trend linking higher education with better child health service utilization.

2 □ Work Engagement vs. Child Deworming (Marginally Significant)

Households where caregivers were more **engaged in work** showed slightly higher likelihood of their children being dewormed.

Possible Explanations:

- **Employed caregivers** may have **greater financial capacity** to travel to facilities, even when deworming is free.
- They may also have **higher opportunity exposure** to health messages in workplaces or social gatherings.
- Conversely, **work engagement might correlate with time constraints**, but in this dataset, it showed a marginally positive effect, possibly due to better **planning or shared caregiving roles** in working households.

Supporting Literature:

- Muthoni and Kabiru (2018) indicated that in Kenya, working mothers had **better immunization compliance**, possibly due to better health knowledge and social exposure.
- Tsawe et al. (2015) also found a positive link between employment and maternal health-seeking behavior in Southern Africa

Other Variables: Statistically Insignificant Relationships

Variables including child **sex**, **source of income**, **household size**, **number of under-five children**, **distance from facility**, and **caregiver relationship** did not show significant associations with:

- Receipt of **vaccinations**
- Receipt of **deworming**
- **Missed vaccinations or deworming**
- **Satisfaction levels**
- **Card retention**
- **Full immunization**

Interpretation:

- These findings suggest that **structural or service-related factors** (e.g., stock-outs, facility

readiness, cold chain, outreach presence) may play a **more dominant role** than household demographics in influencing service uptake in the study area.

- The **lack of effect of distance** may reflect either **urban or semi-urban clustering**, where most respondents live within reachable distances, or that outreach efforts have **partially bridged physical access gaps**.
- Similarly, **household size and number of under-five children** might not affect uptake if services are delivered efficiently and caregivers are aware of their responsibilities.

Literature Insights:

- Lakew et al. (2015) in Ethiopia found distance to be important in rural contexts, but not in peri-urban or urban settings.
- Tadesse et al. (2020) concluded that while household size can be a burden, it only becomes a barrier in areas with **service delivery limitations** or **financial constraints**, which might not be highly variable across your sampled group.

Recommendations Based on These Findings:

- **Focus behavior change communication** (BCC) strategies on less educated caregivers through community volunteers or religious gatherings.
- Consider **work schedule-adjusted outreach** for caregivers with high work engagement.
- Enhance system-level improvements (e.g., addressing vaccine and deworming stock-outs), which may have **greater impact than addressing household-level variations**.
- Further **qualitative work** could explore why certain sociodemographic variables don't seem to influence uptake—perhaps due to uniform exposure or hidden enabling/disabling factors.

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11. HEALTH POLICYMAKER INTERVIEWS – FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings:

Six policymakers were interviewed on child immunization and deworming. Key themes emerged:

Current Implementation Strategies:Routine immunization (all 6 respondents) Periodic campaigns (4 respondents), Big Catch-Up or BIRI campaigns (5 respondents confirmed implementation). **Challenges Identified:** Stockouts and supply disruptions (5 respondents) ,Caregiver awareness gaps and misinformation (3 respondents) Inadequate logistics and cold chain issues (2 respondents) , Staff shortages and training gaps (4 respondents) . **Monitoring and Tracking Mechanisms:**Use of EPI registers, HMIS reports, DHS surveys (all 6) and Supervision and feedback sessions (3 respondents) .**Collaboration and Partnership:**Key partners included WHO, MSF, OWDA, and CHI ,Multi-stakeholder platforms exist with SRHB. **Future Recommendations:** Expand outreach and mobile units, Strengthen cold chain systems, Raise public awareness via media and campaigns

Discussion:

The policymakers' responses highlight key systemic issues that affect immunization and deworming efforts. The recognition of BIRI/Big Catch-Up campaigns reflects alignment with global efforts post-COVID-19 disruptions (WHO, 2023). However, issues of stockouts and caregiver misinformation continue to limit impact (UNICEF, 2022). Strengthening supply chains, expanding digital tracking, and integrating partner support from WHO, MSF, OWDA, and CHI (community health initiatives)are crucial to scale success.

I2: HEALTH WORKER INTERVIEWS – FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings:

A total of 11 health workers were interviewed across multiple facilities.

1. **Main Challenges Reported:**
 - o Poor awareness and low caregiver commitment (7 respondents)
 - o Vaccine stockouts (1)
 - o Power shortages (1)
 - o Geographical challenges (1)
2. **Vaccine Monitoring and Tracking Methods:**
 - o Registers/tally sheets/cards (3 respondents)
 - o History checking (5)
 - o Supervision/home visits (2)
3. **Outreach Services Presence:**
 - o Yes: 7 facilities
 - o No: 4 facilities
4. **Awareness Creation Methods:**

- o Public microphone announcements (6)
- o Educating mothers at health facilities (4)
- o Integrating with campaigns (1)

5. Support Needed for Improvement:

- o Training (9 respondents)
- o Improved logistics and stock availability (3)

Discussion:

Health workers affirmed that while routine services are functional, barriers like caregiver resistance and gaps in awareness persist. The reliance on manual methods like cards and registers limits effective tracking, calling for digital solutions (JSI, 2020). Outreach services play a pivotal role in hard-to-reach areas, aligning with the WHO Reaching Every District strategy (WHO, 2017). Training and logistic reinforcements are urgent needs expressed consistently.

13: HEALTH FACILITY OBSERVATION FINDINGS

Observational Gaps (%) by Facility:

Facility	Gap %
Karamarda	12.5%
Ayardaga	12.5%
Kordhere	50%
Dudohido	34%
Madina	29%
Dr. Abdisalan	33%

chart on facility gap

Observed units included vaccine/deworming card availability, completeness, stock sufficiency, cold chain status, register status, expiration checks, and caregiver education.

Discussion:

Kordhere showed the largest gap (50%), indicating poor inventory or service practices. In contrast, hospitals like Karamarda exhibited more robust practices. This supports WHO's classification of functional vs. non-functional cold chain and stock systems. Stockouts were also evident through oral confirmation, especially for deworming drugs which were not systemically tracked.

OBSERVED VACCINE STOCK VOLUME AND FACILITY CLASSIFICATION

Stock Volume (Total: 26,857 doses):

Stock volume per facility

Amount /volume per vaccine type

Facility Classification:

- **Karamarda** – Government Hospital
- **Madina** – Privately Owned Primary Hospital

- **Dr. Abdisalan** – MCH Clinic
- **Ayardaga, Kordere, Dudohido** – Government Health Center

Discussion:

Karamarda Hospital holds the largest share of vaccine stock (34%) and can serve as a buffer for redistribution. The classification confirms that primary care facilities like health centers are essential suppliers to privately owned clinics.

SECTION V: VACCINE EXPIRY MANAGEMENT AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Facilities With Near-Expiring Vaccines:

Facility	Vaccines Near Expiry	Expiry Date	Outreach Available
Dr. Abdisalan	IPV, Rota (Nov 2025), OPV, Measles (June 2025)	June–Nov 2025	No
Ayardaga	PCV	Oct 2025	Yes
Kordere	PCV	Oct 2025	Yes
Dudohido	PCV	Oct 2025	Yes

Recommendations:

- **Redistribute** from Dr. Abdisalan to Karamarda Hospital or use in upcoming campaigns. When customer individuals or visiting care givers are small number to finish the volume .
- **Health Centers (Ayardaga, Kordere, Dudohido):** Utilize via outreach or apply FEFO.
- **Track and use PCV stock before October.**

Discussion:

Following WHO's First-Expire-First-Out (FEFO) strategy can minimize wastage. Redistribution to high-demand hospitals or catch-up campaign usage ensures operational continuity. Clinics without outreach (e.g., Dr. Abdisalan) face risk of underutilization unless proper planning is initiated.

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Reconfirmations and observations of vaccination cards in the health. Health facilities of **karamarda, duduhido, ayardaga, madina** was visited for reconfirmations of the cards observed during care givers house visit .the researcher visited the facility and confirmed all the 17% out of 52 vaccine registration cards observed during the visit . no mismatches observed in the selected health facility. A great gap Absence of information ,communication, education (IEC) material are observed and confirmed during health facility visit.

14.Conclusion

This study assessed the coverage, determinants, and barriers related to vaccination and deworming services among children under five in Jigjiga, Ethiopia. The findings revealed high overall vaccination coverage (96.24%) but notably low deworming coverage (42.77%). Specific vaccine uptake varied, with strong coverage for BCG (95%) and PCV3 (93.20%), but weaker rates for Measles2 (70.59%) and IPV2 (70.59%). Full immunization coverage was 68.60%, with 31.40% of children missing at least one vaccine. Awareness remained low at 28%, though a high proportion of caregivers (98%) recognized the importance of immunization and deworming.

Despite high belief in the benefits of immunization, practical barriers were evident: only 24% of caregivers had observed vaccine cards, and just 65% had the capacity to retain them. Logistic regression revealed that caregiver education and employment significantly influenced immunization uptake, while age and child sex were not significant factors. Awareness and exposure to health messages were inconsistently distributed, and distance to health facilities had a marginal influence on access—especially for early vaccines like BCG. Deworming services showed disparities linked to caregiver education, employment, and place of residence.

Health worker and policymaker interviews revealed systemic issues such as supply stock-outs, weak infrastructure (power shortages), low caregiver awareness, and logistical challenges in reaching remote populations. While policymakers have adopted strategies like routine services, campaigns, and mobile teams, implementation gaps persist, particularly due to undertrained staff

and coordination issues.

Statistical analyses supported these findings, with educational level significantly associated with deworming uptake ($p = 0.00794$), and employment status showing marginal significance ($p = 0.09794$). ANOVA revealed no significant variation in deworming coverage across kebeles, suggesting uniform but suboptimal service delivery.

15.Recommendations

- 1. Improve Deworming Program Reach and Integration**
 - o Integrate deworming with existing immunization schedules at health posts and outreach sites.
 - o Prioritize awareness campaigns on deworming's importance, especially in less-educated and rural populations.
- 2. Strengthen Caregiver Education and Empowerment**
 - o Develop targeted health education interventions for caregivers with low education or unemployment.
 - o Promote card retention through visual aids, training, and the provision of waterproof cardholders.
- 3. Enhance Vaccine Supply Chain and Infrastructure**
 - o Ensure consistent availability of vaccines and deworming tablets through improved stock management.
 - o Invest in backup power sources (e.g., solar cold chains) to minimize cold chain disruptions.
- 4. Expand Outreach and Mobile Services**
 - o Scale up mobile vaccination and deworming units, particularly in hard-to-reach kebeles.
 - o Use geographic mapping to identify underserved areas and guide mobile service deployment.
- 5. Support and Train Health Workers Continuously**
 - o Provide regular in-service training on EPI and deworming protocols.
 - o Address motivation and commitment gaps through supportive supervision and incentives.
- 6. Boost Community Engagement and Communication**
 - o Use local influencers, religious leaders, and radio broadcasts to raise awareness.
 - o Deliver consistent health messages across channels to improve caregiver understanding and participation.
- 7. Strengthen Monitoring and Evaluation**
 - o Use real-time data dashboards to track vaccine and deworming uptake and stock levels.
 - o Institutionalize routine microplanning and periodic program reviews at woreda and

kebele levels.

8. Policy-Level Actions

- o Encourage multisectoral coordination (health, education, community development).
- o Allocate dedicated budgets for deworming programs within broader child health strategies.

9. Establishing and Including IEC in health programmes to improve child health.

The dashboard is empty. Tap here to add elements

16. Waypoint map of clumped house holds (kebele hhs) visited for interview, jigiga .the list below are the cordiantes of all visited house holds in jigiga city for interview . few missing coordinates due to device to collect map malfunctioning .

Id	lat_titute	long_titute	Kebele/location/residences
1	9.364463	42.81362	10
2	9.36449	42.81313	10
3	9.364892	42.81241	10
4	9.363832	42.81199	10
5	9.365118	42.81194	10

6	9.365221	42.81081	10
7	9.365054	42.81038	10
8	9.364648	42.81112	10
9	9.36503	42.81171	10
10	9.364281	42.81189	10
11	9.3638	42.81384	10
12	9.3629	42.81411	10
13	9.362478	42.81403	10
14	9.361613	42.81514	10
15	9.362415	42.81615	10
16	9.362915	42.81666	10
17	9.363068	42.81717	10
18	9.36361	42.81717	10
19	9.353871	42.82602	16
20	9.354171	42.82517	16
21	9.354925	42.82516	16
22	9.353957	42.805	16
23	9.353894	42.82653	16
24	9.353443	42.82635	16
25	9.365216	42.81579	10
26	9.3638	42.81384	10
27			10
28			10
29	9.358904	42.93819	6
30	9.359034	42.79236	6
31	9.359529	42.79262	6
32	9.359985	42.79345	6
33	9.360555	42.79415	6
34	9.361145	42.79422	6
35	9.361511	42.81398	10
36	9.361476	42.81344	10
37	9.361256	42.81275	10
38	9.360527	42.81255	10
39	9.35743	42.79116	6
40	9.356729	42.79094	6
41	9.35581	42.79079	6
42	9.354016	42.79081	6
43	9.354857	42.79067	6
44	9.354404	42.79079	6
45	9.347008	42.81318	4
46	9.347006	42.81192	4
47			4
48	9.346068	42.81182	4

49	9.348875	42.79389	1
50	9.346097	42.79384	1
51	9.34641	42.79256	1
52	9.346.221	42.79211	1
53	9.334571	42.7146	1
54	9.345835	42.81427	15
55	9.345758	42.81423	15
56			15
57			15
58			2
59	9.342475	42.79712	3
60	9.342435	42.79794	2
61	9.342814	42.79882	3
62	9.341683	42.79888	3
63	9.340745	42.79853	3
64	9.342841	42.81244	4
65	9.343531	42.81169	4
66	9.34329	42.81075	4
67	9.343601	42.81008	4
68	9.349526	42.79387	1
69	9.349196	42.79342	20
70	9,348,842	42.7915	20
71	9.348812	42.79075	20
72			20
73	9.343502	42.81582	15
74	9.342953	42.81579	15
75	9.342006	42.81603	15
76	9.341005	42.81614	15
77	9.338875	42.79879	3
78	9.339439	42.79888	3
79	9.338574	42.79807	2
80	9.338731	42.79748	2
81			3
82			4
83			4
84			4
85			4
86			4
87	9.353882,1681.	42.83044	16
88	9.355996,1682.0	42.83089	16
89	9.354745,1676	42.83022	16
90	9.35404,1680	42.82981	16
91	,9.3596735,1649.0	42.79521	6

92	,9.359564,1656.0	42.79419	6
93	9.359586,1666.	42.79364	6
94	42.79326	9.359412,1657.	6
95	42.79304	9.360764,1666.	6
96	42.79649	9.367966,1648.0	18
97	42.79628	9.368686,1655.0	18
98	42.79619	9.369731,1645.	18
99	42.79591	9.370253,1638	18
100			5
101	42.7935	9.368939,1657.0	18
102	42.79392	9.369036,1661.0	18
103	42.79427	9.369328,1643.	18
104	42.79491	9.369569,1658	18
105	42.7954	9.369902,1656	18
106	9.371044	42.7911	7
107	9.371079	42.79014	7
108	9.37052	42.78959	7
109	9.369951	42.79003	7
110	9.369597	42.70066	7
111	9.339744	42.77811	7
112	9.36732	42.78896	7
113	9.369533	42.78809	7
114	9.369457	42.78747	7
S	9.358184	42.80512	5
116	9.358052	42.80238	5
117	9.358054	42.80238	5
118	9.359262	42.80512	5
119	9.359486	42.80543	5
120	9.359513	42.80542	5
121	9.360099	42.80494	5
122	9.350199	42.79865	5
123	9.36513	42.80227	5
124	9.36422	42.8015	5
125			5
126	9.36513	42.79968	5
127		42.79993,	5
128	9.379848	42.78988	19
129	9.376886	42.78808	19
130			19
131	9.379848	42.78988	19
132	9.378815	42.78957	19
133	9.37806	42.78875	19
134			19

135			19
136	9.352494,1662.0	42.77865	12
137	9.353123,1658.0	42.77805	12
138	9.35378,1664.0	42.77821	12
139	9.354304,1678.0	42.77797	12
140	9.354839,1678.0	42.77802	12
141	9.355218,1664.	42.77845	12
142	9.355275,1683.0	42.77905	12
143	9.354758,1669.0	42.77984	12
144	9.352964,1687.0	42.77976	12
145	9.349484,1661.	42.78281	20
146	9.348793,1656.	42.78276	20
147	9.348325,1663	42.78265	20
148	9.347789,1659	42.78281	9
149	9.346576,1661	42.78252	9
150	9.345369,1653.0	42.78241	9
151	9.344904,1652.0	42.78265	9
152	9.350694,1669.0	42.77153	13
153	9.35068,1662.0	42.77116	13
153	9.351035,1662.0	42.77055	13
155	9.350671,1655.0	42.77003	13
156	9.349879,1659.0	42.7699	13
157	9.34934,1665.0	42.77017	13
158	9.3493185,1662.0	42.76983	13
159	9.348924,1653.0	42.76983	13
160	9.348921,1653.0	42.76925	13
161	9.348793,1646.0	42.7688	13
162	9.348322,1643.0	42.76838	13
162	9.348004,1647.0	42.76777	13
164	9.348048,1646.0	42.76738	13
165	9.370117,1702.0	42.75947	11
166	9.369215,1682.0	42.75899	11
167	9.368997,1690.0	42.75928	11
168	9.368492,1695.0	42.759773,	11
169	9.367865,1696.0	42.76052	11
170	9.367362,1673.0	42.76017	11
171	9.366699,1690.0	42.76041	11
172	9.366866,1709.0	42.76097	11
173	9.367594,1696.0	42.76149	11
174	9.366801,1689.0	42.7627	11
175	9.369694,1652.0	42.80474	17
176	9.36948,1631.0	42.80595	17

177	9.368905,1664.0	42.80585	17
178	9.36783,1661.0	42.80554	17
179	9.367069,1651.0	42.80559	17
180	9.366698,1659.0	42.8053	17
181	9.384673,1674.0	42.80226	19
182	9.385406,1674.0	42.80186	19
183	9.388306	42.80189	19
184	9.388312,1683.0	42.8019	19
185	9.388972,1671.0	42.80138	19
190	9.38998,1670.0	42.800842,	19
191	9.390398,1678.0	42.80039	19
192	9.390695,1686.0	42.79987	19
193	9.391429,1690.0	42.79965	19
194	9.39269,1672.0	42.79994	19
195	9.393262,1694.0	42.80033	19
196	9.393029,1687.0	42.80125	19
197	9.343838,1614.0	42.79601	1
198	9.341647,1623.0	42.79673	2
199	9.34136,1626.0	42.7968	2
200	9.340552,1626.0	42.79673	2
201	9.339417,1631.0	42.79671	2
202	9.338841,1608.0	42.79683	2
203	9.338373,1602.0	42.7969	2
204	9.338381,1614.0	42.79696	2
205	9.338901,1618.0	42.7973	2
206	9.339473,1622.0	42.79736	2
207	9.3758545,1658.0	42.80695	17
208	9.376634,1648.0	42.80754	17
209	9.377023,1654.0	42.80783	17
2010	9.377879,1652.0	42.8086	17
211	9.378375,1648.0	42.80904	17
212	9.37889,1671.0	42.80942	17
213	9.378953,1660.0	42.80959	17
214	9.380468,1661.0	42.81055	17
215	9.381012,1666.0	42.81161	17
216	9.381897,1659.0	42.81224	17
217	9.382926,1643.0	42.81274	17

ANEXX

Comprehensive Table: Vaccines and Deworming Medications for Children

Abbreviation	Full Name	Protects Against	Type	Schedule (Ethiopia EPI)	Route
BCG	Bacillus Calmette-Guérin	Tuberculosis (esp. TB meningitis, miliary TB)	Live attenuated	At birth	Intradermal injection
OPV	Oral Polio Vaccine	Poliomyelitis	Live attenuated (oral)	Birth (OPV0), 6, 10, 14 weeks	Oral drops
IPV	Inactivated Polio Vaccine	Poliomyelitis (boosts immunity)	Inactivated virus	14 weeks (IPV 1), sometimes IPV2	Intramuscular injection
Penta	Pentavalent Vaccine	Diphtheria, Pertussis, Tetanus, Hepatitis B, Hib	Combination vaccine	6, 10, 14 weeks	Intramuscular injection
Rota	Rotavirus Vaccine	Rotavirus diarrhea	Live attenuated	6 and 10 weeks	Oral drops
PCV	Pneumococcal Conjugate Vaccine	Pneumonia, meningitis, sepsis (Streptococcus pneumoniae)	Conjugate vaccine	6, 10, 14 weeks	Intramuscular injection
Measles	Measles Vaccine (MCV)	Measles (rash, pneumonia, complications)	Live attenuated	9 months (Measles 1), 15 months (Measles 2)	Subcutaneous injection
<i>(No Abbrev.)</i>	Albendazole	Intestinal worms (broad-spectrum)	Antiparasitic medication	At 12 months, every 6 months	Oral (tablet/syrup)

		deworming)			
(No Abbrev.)	Mebendazole	Intestinal worms (alternative to Albendazole)	Antiparasitic medication	At 12 months, every 6 months	Oral (tablet/syrup)

Abbreviations

P= probability value

HH = house hold

BIRI=booster immunizations and rapid intensifications

FIFO= first in first out

Vvm vaccine vial monitor

EPI + expanded immunization programme

CHI= community health initiative

OWDA= organizations for welfare and development in action

MSF= medecins sans frontiers

SRHB= somali regional health bureau

IEC: information, Educations and communications .

Rota + rota vaccines

MCV= measles containing vaccines

HHI	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
1	1	0.47%	0.47%	
2	1	0.47%	0.94%	
3	1	0.47%	1.42%	

4	1	0.47%	1.89%	
5	1	0.47%	2.36%	
6	1	0.47%	2.83%	
7	1	0.47%	3.30%	
8	1	0.47%	3.77%	
9	1	0.47%	4.25%	
10	1	0.47%	4.72%	
11	1	0.47%	5.19%	
12	1	0.47%	5.66%	
13	1	0.47%	6.13%	
14	1	0.47%	6.60%	
15	1	0.47%	7.08%	
16	1	0.47%	7.55%	
17	1	0.47%	8.02%	
18	1	0.47%	8.49%	
19	1	0.47%	8.96%	
20	1	0.47%	9.43%	
21	1	0.47%	9.91%	
22	1	0.47%	10.38%	
23	1	0.47%	10.85%	
24	1	0.47%	11.32%	
25	1	0.47%	11.79%	
26	1	0.47%	12.26%	
27	1	0.47%	12.74%	
28	1	0.47%	13.21%	
29	1	0.47%	13.68%	
30	1	0.47%	14.15%	

31	1	0.47%	14.62%	
32	1	0.47%	15.09%	
33	1	0.47%	15.57%	
34	1	0.47%	16.04%	
35	1	0.47%	16.51%	
36	1	0.47%	16.98%	
37	1	0.47%	17.45%	
38	1	0.47%	17.92%	
39	1	0.47%	18.40%	
40	1	0.47%	18.87%	
41	1	0.47%	19.34%	
42	1	0.47%	19.81%	
43	1	0.47%	20.28%	
44	1	0.47%	20.75%	
45	1	0.47%	21.23%	
46	1	0.47%	21.70%	
47	1	0.47%	22.17%	
48	1	0.47%	22.64%	
49	1	0.47%	23.11%	
50	1	0.47%	23.58%	
51	1	0.47%	24.06%	
52	1	0.47%	24.53%	
53	1	0.47%	25.00%	
54	1	0.47%	25.47%	
55	1	0.47%	25.94%	
56	1	0.47%	26.42%	
57	1	0.47%	26.89%	

58	1	0.47%	27.36%	
59	1	0.47%	27.83%	
60	1	0.47%	28.30%	
61	1	0.47%	28.77%	
62	1	0.47%	29.25%	
63	1	0.47%	29.72%	
64	1	0.47%	30.19%	
65	1	0.47%	30.66%	
66	1	0.47%	31.13%	
67	1	0.47%	31.60%	
68	1	0.47%	32.08%	
69	1	0.47%	32.55%	
70	1	0.47%	33.02%	
71	1	0.47%	33.49%	
72	1	0.47%	33.96%	
73	1	0.47%	34.43%	
74	1	0.47%	34.91%	
75	1	0.47%	35.38%	
76	1	0.47%	35.85%	
77	1	0.47%	36.32%	
78	1	0.47%	36.79%	
79	1	0.47%	37.26%	
80	1	0.47%	37.74%	
81	1	0.47%	38.21%	
82	1	0.47%	38.68%	
83	1	0.47%	39.15%	
84	1	0.47%	39.62%	

85	1	0.47%	40.09%	
86	1	0.47%	40.57%	
87	1	0.47%	41.04%	
88	1	0.47%	41.51%	
89	1	0.47%	41.98%	
90	1	0.47%	42.45%	
91	1	0.47%	42.92%	
92	1	0.47%	43.40%	
93	1	0.47%	43.87%	
94	1	0.47%	44.34%	
95	1	0.47%	44.81%	
96	1	0.47%	45.28%	
97	1	0.47%	45.75%	
98	1	0.47%	46.23%	
99	1	0.47%	46.70%	
100	1	0.47%	47.17%	
101	1	0.47%	47.64%	
102	1	0.47%	48.11%	
103	1	0.47%	48.58%	
104	1	0.47%	49.06%	
105	1	0.47%	49.53%	
106	1	0.47%	50.00%	
107	1	0.47%	50.47%	
108	1	0.47%	50.94%	
109	1	0.47%	51.42%	
110	1	0.47%	51.89%	
111	1	0.47%	52.36%	

112	1	0.47%	52.83%	
113	1	0.47%	53.30%	
114	1	0.47%	53.77%	
116	1	0.47%	54.25%	
117	1	0.47%	54.72%	
118	1	0.47%	55.19%	
119	1	0.47%	55.66%	
120	1	0.47%	56.13%	
121	1	0.47%	56.60%	
122	1	0.47%	57.08%	
123	1	0.47%	57.55%	
124	1	0.47%	58.02%	
125	1	0.47%	58.49%	
126	1	0.47%	58.96%	
127	1	0.47%	59.43%	
128	1	0.47%	59.91%	
129	1	0.47%	60.38%	
130	1	0.47%	60.85%	
131	1	0.47%	61.32%	
132	1	0.47%	61.79%	
133	1	0.47%	62.26%	
134	1	0.47%	62.74%	
135	1	0.47%	63.21%	
136	1	0.47%	63.68%	
137	1	0.47%	64.15%	
138	1	0.47%	64.62%	

139	1	0.47%	65.09%	
140	1	0.47%	65.57%	
141	1	0.47%	66.04%	
142	1	0.47%	66.51%	
143	1	0.47%	66.98%	
144	1	0.47%	67.45%	
145	1	0.47%	67.92%	
146	1	0.47%	68.40%	
147	1	0.47%	68.87%	
148	1	0.47%	69.34%	
149	1	0.47%	69.81%	
150	1	0.47%	70.28%	
151	1	0.47%	70.75%	
152	1	0.47%	71.23%	
153	2	0.94%	72.17%	
155	1	0.47%	72.64%	
156	1	0.47%	73.11%	
157	1	0.47%	73.58%	
158	1	0.47%	74.06%	
159	1	0.47%	74.53%	
160	1	0.47%	75.00%	
161	1	0.47%	75.47%	
162	2	0.94%	76.42%	
164	1	0.47%	76.89%	
165	1	0.47%	77.36%	
166	1	0.47%	77.83%	
167	1	0.47%	78.30%	

168	1	0.47%	78.77%	
169	1	0.47%	79.25%	
170	1	0.47%	79.72%	
171	1	0.47%	80.19%	
172	1	0.47%	80.66%	
173	1	0.47%	81.13%	
174	1	0.47%	81.60%	
175	1	0.47%	82.08%	
176	1	0.47%	82.55%	
177	1	0.47%	83.02%	
178	1	0.47%	83.49%	
179	1	0.47%	83.96%	
180	1	0.47%	84.43%	
181	1	0.47%	84.91%	
182	1	0.47%	85.38%	
183	1	0.47%	85.85%	
184	1	0.47%	86.32%	
185	1	0.47%	86.79%	
190	1	0.47%	87.26%	
191	1	0.47%	87.74%	
192	1	0.47%	88.21%	
193	1	0.47%	88.68%	
194	1	0.47%	89.15%	
195	1	0.47%	89.62%	
196	1	0.47%	90.09%	
197	1	0.47%	90.57%	
198	1	0.47%	91.04%	

199	1	0.47%	91.51%	
200	1	0.47%	91.98%	
201	1	0.47%	92.45%	
202	1	0.47%	92.92%	
203	1	0.47%	93.40%	
204	1	0.47%	93.87%	
205	1	0.47%	94.34%	
206	1	0.47%	94.81%	
207	1	0.47%	95.28%	
208	1	0.47%	95.75%	
209	1	0.47%	96.23%	
211	1	0.47%	96.70%	
212	1	0.47%	97.17%	
213	1	0.47%	97.64%	
214	1	0.47%	98.11%	
215	1	0.47%	98.58%	
216	1	0.47%	99.06%	
217	1	0.47%	99.53%	
2010	1	0.47%	100.00%	
Total	212	100.00%	100.00%	

CAREGIVER_ AGE	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
17	1	0.49%	0.49%	
18	2	0.98%	1.47%	

19	3	1.47%	2.94%	
20	12	5.88%	8.82%	
21	3	1.47%	10.29%	
22	9	4.41%	14.71%	
23	10	4.90%	19.61%	
24	7	3.43%	23.04%	
25	19	9.31%	32.35%	
26	9	4.41%	36.76%	
27	9	4.41%	41.18%	
28	7	3.43%	44.61%	
29	7	3.43%	48.04%	
30	44	21.57%	69.61%	
32	9	4.41%	74.02%	
33	4	1.96%	75.98%	
34	2	0.98%	76.96%	
35	18	8.82%	85.78%	
36	3	1.47%	87.25%	
37	3	1.47%	88.73%	
38	5	2.45%	91.18%	
39	1	0.49%	91.67%	
40	8	3.92%	95.59%	
42	1	0.49%	96.08%	

43	1	0.49%	96.57%	
45	1	0.49%	97.06%	■
47	1	0.49%	97.55%	■
48	1	0.49%	98.04%	■
50	2	0.98%	99.02%	■
52	1	0.49%	99.51%	■
60	1	0.49%	100.00%	■
Total	204	100.00%	100.00%	■
				■

TOTALHHSNUMBER	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent	
2	2	0.96%	0.96%	
3	30	14.35%	15.31%	
4	30	14.35%	29.67%	

5	28	13.40%	43.06%	
6	35	16.75%	59.81%	
7	27	12.92%	72.73%	
8	18	8.61%	81.34%	
9	11	5.26%	86.60%	
10	10	4.78%	91.39%	
11	7	3.35%	94.74%	
12	5	2.39%	97.13%	
13	1	0.48%	97.61%	
14	3	1.44%	99.04%	
15	2	0.96%	100.00%	
Total	209	100.00%	100.00%	

